

PREFIGURE

Prototypes for addressing the housing-energy-nexus

Deliverable 2.1: In-Depth Prototype Profiles

WP 2 - Prototypes of Change – Social, Political and Market Innovations for improving the Housing and Energy Nexus

Authors:

Maria Kaika (UvA) *, Georgia Alexandri (KIT) **, Aysegül Can (KIT) **, Mendel Giezen (UvA) **, Michael Janoschka (KIT) **

*First author

** Second authors, in equal contribution weight

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Executive Summary

This report presents the research findings of the first phase of the PREFIGURE project (months 1–10, Work Package 2). PREFIGURE was developed in response to the pressing political and economic challenges related to housing inequalities and the need for a just energy transition in European cities. It introduces an ambitious and innovative approach to identifying, analysing, and linking “Prototypes of Change” – social, political, and economic practices aimed at fostering innovation, supporting affordable housing renovation, and tackling energy poverty. By focusing on solutions that benefit vulnerable households and communities, the project aims to create more inclusive and sustainable housing systems.

Work Package 2 seeks to identify and analyse these active and emerging Prototypes of Change. These prototypes, whether top-down or bottom-up, challenge conventional, path-dependent approaches and explore new ways to address inequalities in the Energy-Housing Nexus.

The report presents 12 Prototypes of Change studied by the PREFIGURE consortium, providing:

- 1) Insights into their incentives, drivers, barriers, and potential future evolution;
- 2) A preliminary assessment of their capacity to address housing precarity and energy poverty;
- 3) An initial typology with actionable insights for policy makers.

This is a first step towards the development of policy guidelines, which will later be integrated into Work Package 3, consisting of a comparative analysis of structural housing and energy inequalities in national, regional, and local contexts. This analysis will consider the constraints, challenges, and changes within housing policies, markets, and governance systems.

By generating original empirical data and exploring alternative knowledge practices, this report aims to inform the decision-making of citizens, social actors, market actors, and policy-makers, thereby contributing significantly to PREFIGURE’s key outcome: the development of tailored policy recommendations for a wide range of stakeholders that promote more equitable and sustainable housing solutions. By bridging research and practice, the project aims to inform and influence policies that drive systemic change in the housing and energy sectors.

1. PREFIGURE's Scope and Objectives: Exploring "Prototypes of Change" to Address the Housing/Energy-Inequality-Nexus.

Access to affordable housing has become an escalating challenge, disproportionately affecting low-income groups, single-parent households, ethnic minorities, and refugees. At the same time, rising inflation and energy costs deepen social vulnerability, while the financialisation of both energy and housing systems reinforces the link between energy and housing vulnerability. PREFIGURE responds to these societal challenges with regard to the inequalities entrenched in the Housing-Energy Nexus by identifying, researching, comparing, and contrasting a number of emerging "Prototypes of Change", namely, alternative, innovative social, political, and economic practices that seek to facilitate affordable housing renovation while alleviating energy poverty and/or providing green energy solutions. By conducting quantitative and qualitative research to examine these initiatives within their specific local social and economic contexts, PREFIGURE promotes a nuanced understanding of the potential role that such alternative practices can play in transforming housing and energy policies and systems. More specifically, PREFIGURE:

- **Identifies and analyses 14 Prototypes of Change:** We explore their origin and trajectory, reasons for their establishment, objectives, and effectiveness in reducing housing inequalities and energy poverty.
- **Conducts a comparative structural analysis:** Within each prototype's locality, we assess the housing and energy policies, market dynamics, and financial accessibility in national and regional contexts that have influenced the emergence, scope and scalability of each Prototype of Change.
- **Engages in knowledge co-creation, and mobilisation:** We build learning communities and foster cross-country and cross-sector collaboration to support sustainable and inclusive models for addressing housing and energy vulnerability.

The broader **aim of PREFIGURE is to assess the potential of these Prototypes of Change to act as prefigurative politics** that can guide policy makers with guidance and influence the way we think and legislate about energy poverty and housing inequalities in relation to each other. While the transition to sustainable housing and energy systems is often framed as a consolidated and linear shift towards zero emissions, PREFIGURE highlights the importance of focusing on locally grounded, often bottom-up innovations that actively challenge the existing unequal distribution of wealth and resources. Exploring these Prototypes of Change is essential for three main reasons:

1. **Scalability and transferability:** By studying how these innovations work in different

socio-political, cultural, climatic, and geographical contexts, PREFIGURE identifies the mechanisms that enable their adaptation and replication. Understanding these dynamics allows for the up-scaling and multiplication of effective solutions, ensuring that sustainable housing and energy initiatives can be spread beyond isolated pilot projects.

- 2. Interdisciplinary knowledge production:** Prototypes of Change emerge at the intersection of multiple disciplines, requiring an integrated research approach that links housing with political theory, urban sociology, energy transitions and planning. By adopting an inter- and transdisciplinary perspective, PREFIGURE advances the state of the art in housing and sustainability studies, bridging different methodologies to develop holistic solutions.
- 3. Disrupting structural inequalities:** In contrast to top-down policy solutions, which often reinforce existing power dynamics, Prototypes of Change function as disruptive interventions that challenge financialised housing markets, speculative urban development, and exclusionary energy policies. Exploring these prototypes sheds light on the transformative potential of community-led innovation and provides actionable strategies for policymakers seeking to promote a just transition.

By pursuing these three objectives, PREFIGURE ensures that its research contributes to the mainstreaming and integration of alternative housing and energy models into broader governance frameworks, rather than merely documenting them. The insights gained from analysing Prototypes of Change thus provide crucial evidence for shaping inclusive and socially just housing transitions.

This report explores the scope and potential of Prototypes of Change, serving as a foundational step in providing actionable guidance for policymakers. It begins with a concise yet comprehensive summary of the 12 Prototypes of Change that were examined in the project.

This deliverable will not deal with the 2 prototypes from Estonia, due to an internal change of the consortium. The research in Estonia will be carried on by a new Estonian partner who will officially enter the PREFIGURE consortium after the submission of this deliverable and take over the analysis of two local studies in Tallin and Tartu.

It then situates the research within the broader contextual aims and theoretical framework of PREFIGURE, followed by an exploration of the two key socio-political challenges that it addresses. Next, the report details the methodological approach that was used for the qualitative, ethnographic and in-depth research on the prototypes and introduces the common research framework and research questions that were designed to ensure comparability across cases. The subsequent presentation of an exhaustive analysis of the qualitative and ethnographic findings for each prototype emphasises their driving factors and contributions to the mitigation of housing and energy inequalities. The report concludes with a discussion of the potential contributions of the prototypes to the development of significant comparative research and the basis for policy recommendations in the subsequent phases of PREFIGURE.

2. Twelve Prototypes of Change - A Synopsis

In this section, a concise synopsis of each prototype selected by the six project partners is provided, thereby enabling the reader to acquire a preliminary understanding of the case studies. A more detailed analysis of each prototype, incorporating the research questions, methods, and theoretical foundations that informed their selection, is presented subsequently in this report (Section 9).

Prototype 1 – Refugee squats and self-housing (Thessaloniki GR – UvA)

A substantial body of research examines the living conditions within state-run refugee camps; However, little is known about refugee access to adequate energy and affordable housing outside of these camps. PREFIGURE analyses collective actions and solidarity initiatives designed to address the energy poverty and substandard housing quality experienced by refugees in Greece. Moreover, the research focuses on self-housing and squatting arrangements by refugees, located in underprivileged neighbourhoods in city centres, mostly taxonomized in a low energy class, incurring high energy costs that refugees struggle to cover.

Prototype 2 – Christiania (Copenhagen, DK - MAU)

Christiania, an autonomous neighbourhood in the center of Copenhagen, Denmark. Established in 1971 by activists and artists, it functions on the principles of collective ownership of land and assets, emphasizing affordability and self-governance. The housing is non-commodified, with rents way below the average for the area, funding community needs, and homes maintained by residents. The *Nabovarme* project, initiated in 2001, introduced renewable energy solutions, transforming heating into a collective effort using wood pellets, solar energy, and geothermal systems integrated into a Thermonet. By prioritising renewable energy sources, practices involving Do-It-Yourself (DIY) initiatives and collective strategies, Christiania offers an innovative community-driven prototype for addressing the Housing-Energy Nexus.

Prototype 3 – CommonEN (Ioannina, GR - IMPERIAL)

The energy cooperative CommonEn, established in 2021 in Ioannina, Greece, launched its first solar park in 2023. This initiative has the capacity to provide electricity to 35 households and local small and medium enterprises (SMEs). Supported by the organisation Electra Energy, the cooperative is dedicated to promoting sustainable energy and addressing energy poverty. Operating in a region characterised by high unemployment and an ageing population, CommonEn represents a grassroots social innovation for community-centred energy solutions.

Prototype 4 – WG Ketelhuis (Amsterdam, NL - UVA)

The WG-Ketelhuis project in Amsterdam is a community-driven energy initiative established in 2018 with the objective of transitioning a central neighbourhood from gas-based heating to the utilisation of heat sourced from nearby canals, which is stored underground and distributed via heat pumps for year-round heating. The project emphasises common ownership, democratic decision-making, and a Do-It-With-Others (DIWO) approach, fostering social cohesion and empowering residents to govern their energy needs. As a prototype of social and frugal innovation, WG-Ketelhuis addresses energy inequities by offering a cost-effective, sustainable, and community-led alternative to traditional energy systems.

Prototype 5 – Barcelona digital Platform for sharing information on Housing Conditions- Reviu (Barcelona, ESP, IDRA)

Reviu is an online platform launched in 2024 in Barcelona by the IDRA cooperative, facilitating the exchange of reviews from tenants on the quality of rental apartments and landlords. The platform was developed to address the shortcomings in housing equity and transparency within Spain's rental sector, by incorporating tenant perspectives. The evaluation encompasses aspects such as housing quality, thermal comfort, rent fairness, and landlord communication. The application of Reviu can be considered both a technological innovation and a communing practice, with the potential to foster a collaborative tenant community while promoting accountability in the rental sector.

Prototype 6 – Non-profit Housing Associations (Denmark, DK - MAU)

Non-profit housing associations (NPHAs) in Denmark provide affordable, democratically governed housing for approximately 20% of the population, supported by state subsidies and municipal oversight. Governed by tenant-elected boards, these associations ensure cost-based rents and cater to diverse social groups, including students, the elderly, and the disabled. The sector also fosters energy communities, as evidenced by Øbro95, where residents, with support from the municipality and green software developer Enyday, installed solar panels and a battery system. While this model promotes sustainability and cost optimisation, challenges such as financing and scalability in less affluent areas remain critical issues for broader implementation.

Prototype 7 – WikiHousing (Barcelona, ESP - IDRA)

WikiHousing is a participatory initiative in Barcelona that delivers affordable, sustainable public housing through co-design and community involvement. The initiative was founded by architects David Baró and David Juárez, with the objective of addressing the issue of housing affordability. The project utilises light-weight balloon frame construction and modular design, representing an innovative approach to the challenges posed by the availability of land, housing and energy in the city. Supported by the city's BIT Habitat Foundation, its aims at empowering residents to co-create and manage their homes. In this way, WikiHousing combines blending technological innovation with participatory governance to promote community-led urban design.

Prototype 8 – Brixton Energy (London, UK - IMPERIAL)

Brixton Energy, a citizen-led cooperative based in South London, is an organisation that promotes clean, renewable energy sources while ensuring tangible benefits for the local community. Through active com-

munity engagement, shareholder participation, and the creation of green jobs, Brixton Energy reinvests its profits into a Community Energy Efficiency Fund (CEEF) to further its impact. Operating as a community-owned cooperative, it collaborates with the local borough administration, which provides financial and institutional support, fostering sustainable, community-centred energy solutions.

Prototype 9 – CODE HOUSING Microloans (Burgas, BG - CSD)

Habitat Bulgaria, a constituent element of the global Habitat for Humanity network, is dedicated to the enhancement of living conditions for vulnerable families through the provision of affordable housing, advocacy, and energy efficiency initiatives. In 2022, it initiated the CODE HOUSING programme, offering microfinance solutions and life skills workshops to improve housing and community resilience in six Bulgarian cities. The programme promotes energy efficiency through both basic and renewable energy solutions, fostering community empowerment and collaboration with local NGOs, authorities, and experts. The CODE HOUSING initiative is noteworthy for its comprehensive approach, integrating financial innovation, capacity building, and sustainable development for marginalised communities.

Prototype 10 – One Stop Shop (Bulgaria, BG - CSD)

Bulgaria's one-stop-shop (OSS) initiatives for housing/ energy upgrades highlights a service model that facilitates energy efficiency and renewable energy improvements for residential buildings. The establishment of the first municipal energy centres in Gabrovo and Burgas has been instrumental in consolidating expert advice, financial assistance, and regulatory guidance, thereby making energy upgrades accessible to low-income families. The centres have been found to empower citizens through the facilitation of workshops, whilst reducing administrative barriers and promoting sustainable solutions that ensure cost-effective home improvements. This initiative is part of the Bulgarian Recovery and Resilience Plan, which aims to make energy-efficient renovations both achievable and sustainable for all.

Prototype 11 – Housing Thessaloniki (Thessaloniki, GR - KIT)

The pilot programme Housing Thessaloniki, Greece, has been devised to address both the housing crisis and energy poverty by renovating 30 apartments into safe, affordable, and energy-efficient publicly-owned housing. Vacant and underused properties have been identified as the target of this initiative, with the aim of integrating them into a network of affordable housing for low-income households. A collaborative effort involving state bodies, local organisations, and the municipality, presents a sustainable alternative to the conventional housing market by providing immediate relief and long-term solutions for housing insecurity.

Prototype 12 – Energy Districts (Karlsruhe, DE – KIT)

The KfW432 subsidy in Germany, which was available to citizens from 2011 to 2024, supported the creation of energy districts under the “energy efficient urban redevelopment” programme by KfW Bank. Following the subsidy's termination in 2024, the Karlsruhe Energy and Climate Protection Agency (KEK), a non-profit organisation established by the city, has continued to promote energy districts. The primary focus of the KEK has been on the provision of advisory services to households in these districts, initially through direct visits and more recently through the establishment of information points and the dissemination of information materials via postal mail. This ensures the ongoing implementation of energy efficiency initiatives in urban redevelopment.

3. Contextualising the Prototypes of Change: Insights from Political Economy and Urban Political Ecology

As stated in the introduction, in order to comprehend the capacity of the prototypes to function as paradigms for prefigurative politics, it is necessary to direct attention not solely to the prototypes themselves, but also to the manner in which local economic, cultural and social contexts – which give rise to housing inequality and energy vulnerability – are interconnected with the emergence of these alternative practices. To this end, a dual conceptual framework is employed, integrating Political Economy and Urban Political Ecology.

3.1 Insights from Political Economy

The present study aims to demonstrate how it is possible to understand the emergence of each Prototype of Change as a response to local, regional, and national housing and energy inequalities. To this end, each prototype is embedded within the political economy of housing and energy markets and institutions in each case study country and city. Our findings reveal that over the past years, housing and energy vulnerability has been profoundly reshaped by financialisation, deregulated lending practices, and market-driven policies that prioritise market solutions and real estate as a financial asset rather than a social necessity¹.

To contextualise the framework of the current housing affordability crisis, we drive attention to the literature of housing financialisation and the way this further relates to the energy crisis. While the body of literature on housing financialisation has expanded considerably over the past decade, shaping the discourse on post-crisis urban restructuring, its roots can be traced to the commodification of housing provision². The state has emerged as a key agent in facilitating this process, with attention directed towards housing policy deregulation, financial sector expansion, and the coordinated actions of multiple levels of government to integrate local real estate into global financial markets³. The state's withdrawal from active welfare policies related to housing has coincided with the liberalisation of financial markets⁴, encouraging households –including low-income groups previously excluded from capital markets– to pursue homeownership through mortgage debt⁵. The global financial crisis further accelerated these dynamics, as financial institutions holding non-performing assets such as mortgages,

¹ Aalbers, M.B., 2016. *Financialization of Housing*. London and New York: Taylor & Francis.

² Forrest, R. and Hirayama, Y., 2015. The financialisation of the social project: Embedded liberalism, neoliberalism and home ownership. *Urban Studies*, 52(2), pp.233-244.

³ Çelik, Ö., 2023. The roles of the state in the financialisation of housing in Turkey. *Housing Studies*, 38(6), pp.1006-1026.

⁴ Aalbers, M.B. and Christophers, B., 2014. Centring housing in political economy. *Housing, theory and society*, 31(4), pp.373-394.

⁵ Krippner, G.R., 2005. The financialization of the American economy. *Socio-economic review*, 3(2), pp.173-208.

loans, and securities benefited from acquiring full property rights⁶. Concurrently, fiscal retrenchment at local and regional government levels has been addressed through the privatisation of public assets and the sale of social housing stock⁷. Furthermore, the deregulation of tenant protections, alongside policy reforms in the private rental sector, including tax exemptions and provisions allowing tax contributions to be shifted elsewhere, has attracted significant interest from transnational investors⁸.

Financial investment companies, such as private equity firms, Real Estate Investment Trusts (REITs), and publicly listed real estate corporations that own or manage residential properties, have become key players in an increasing number of local housing markets. Driven primarily by the goal of maximising dividends for shareholders⁹, these companies focus on the profit-generating characteristics of housing, treating it similarly to interest-bearing capital investments¹⁰. Profit is principally achieved through rent maximisation strategies¹¹, including: **(i)** the identification of investment opportunities in potential rent gaps – the difference between current and potential ground rent when land use shifts towards more profitable activities¹²; **(ii)** the increase in rents without necessarily improving the housing stock¹³; **(iii)** the conducting of minor maintenance and renovations that boost property values and allow justification for higher rents, attracting tenants who can afford more than previous occupants¹⁴; and **(iv)** reinvestment in capital market instruments, such as securities and mortgages backed by housing assets, enabling the acquisition of additional credit to fuel further market expansion¹⁵.

Furthermore, market expansion has been reinforced by a shift from short-term speculative strategies centred on ‘buying low and selling high’ to the adoption of long-term rent extraction strategies, often referred to as “housing financialisation 2.0”¹⁶. This approach focuses on securing sustained, and often increasing, rental income streams through several key practices: **(i)** incorporating maintenance costs and additional service fees directly into rent calculations; **(ii)** leveraging online platforms to manage assets efficiently, reducing communication and operational costs, while using tenant credit scores to tailor rent increases based on household income¹⁷; **(iii)** targeting housing-welfare recipients, as state-provided benefits ensure stable rent payments¹⁸; and **(iv)** investing in emerging residential models, such as build-to-rent developments for families and professionals, which often feature shared amenities

⁶ García-Lamarca, M. & Kaika, M., 2016. ‘Mortgaged lives’: the biopolitics of debt and housing financialisation. *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers*, 41(3), pp.313-327; Alexandri, G. & Janoschka, M., 2018. Who loses and who wins in a housing crisis? Lessons from Spain and Greece for a nuanced understanding of dispossession. *Housing Policy Debate*, 28(1), pp.117-134.

⁷ Hodkinson, S., 2020. *Safe as houses: Private greed, political negligence and housing policy after Grenfell*. Manchester University Press.

⁸ Aalbers, M.B., 2018. Financial geography I: Geographies of tax. *Progress in Human Geography*, 42(6), pp.916-927.

⁹ Van der Zwan, N., 2014. Making sense of financialization. *Socio-economic review*, 12(1), pp.99-129.

¹⁰ Aalbers, M.B. and Christophers, B., 2014 *op.cit.*; Adkins, L., Cooper, M. & Konings, M., 2020 *op.cit.*

¹¹ Haila, A., 2016. *Urban land rent: Singapore as a property state*. New York: John Wiley & Sons.

¹² Christophers, B., 2021. Mind the rent gap: Blackstone, housing investment and the reordering of urban rent surfaces. *Urban Studies*, 59(4), pp. 698-716.

¹³ Janoschka, M., Alexandri, G., Ramos, H.O. & Vives-Miró, S., 2020. Tracing the socio-spatial logics of transnational landlords’ real estate investment: Blackstone in Madrid. *European Urban and Regional Studies*, 27(2), pp.125-141.

¹⁴ Haila, A., 2016. *Urban land rent: Singapore as a property state*. New York: John Wiley & Sons.

¹⁵ Gotham, K.F., 2009. Creating liquidity out of spatial fixity: The secondary circuit of capital and the subprime mortgage crisis. *International journal of urban and regional research*, 33(2), pp.355-371.

¹⁶ Wijburg, G., Aalbers, M.B. & Heeg, S., 2018. The financialisation of rental housing 2.0: Releasing housing into the privatised mainstream of capital accumulation. *Antipode*, 50(4), pp.1098-1119.

¹⁷ Janoschka, M., Alexandri, G., Ramos, H.O. & Vives-Miró, S., 2020 *op.cit.*

¹⁸ Bernt, M., Colini, L. & Förste, D., 2017. Privatization, financialization and state restructuring in Eastern Germany: The case of Am Südpark. *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research*, 41(4), pp.555-571.

like swimming pools, playgrounds, and gyms; purpose-built student accommodations; elderly housing; serviced apartments for highly mobile, well-paid professionals; and co-living arrangements designed for early-career employees, students, and single-person households¹⁹.

In parallel, the implementation of macroprudential regulations designed to restrict mortgage access, has compounded the challenges faced by households in securing credit financing for property ownership²⁰. At the end of the phase of quantitative easing, procured by central banks as a monetary policy to encourage consumption and investment until 2022, mounting evidence suggests that the resulting 'wall of liquidity' has catalysed a search for high-yielding and secure investment opportunities²¹. Residential real estate, particularly in large cities, emerged as a highly attractive asset class for both domestic and international investors. Over the past decade, housing has absorbed a substantial portion of global excess liquidity, leading to a significant accumulation of house price increases²². This phenomenon can be attributed to the process of financialisation, which enabled individuals to leverage larger mortgage loans to acquire more expensive homes. Concurrently, preceding generations of homeowners experienced benefits, given that wealth increased in proportion to property values, and low-interest borrowing facilitated the mobilisation of housing wealth for the acquisition of additional dwellings for rental purposes²³. Nevertheless, the consequence of this competitive spiral has been to extend property prices beyond the financial reach of those with middle and lower incomes, as well as for market entrants who are latecomers (ibid). These trends are particularly salient in terms of their generational implications, giving rise to the notion of intergenerational injustice. In essence, this can be understood as a scenario in which the quantitative easing that has been implemented has resulted in the accumulation of wealth for the owners of financial housing assets, while concomitantly placing pressure on the younger generation, who are reliant on labour income, to shoulder greater financial burdens.

Recent research has increasingly highlighted the intersections between housing financialisation and the ongoing energy crisis, shedding light on how financial investors are capitalising on new forms of household vulnerability. As energy costs have surged, exacerbating the financial strain on households, particularly in low-income and precarious housing situations, utility debt has emerged as an additional vector for financial extraction. Financial actors have adapted their investment strategies to account for the rising utility costs and have also actively sought to capture value from household energy debt through mechanisms such as the securitization of unpaid utility bills. In this process, debt is bundled into financial products and traded on secondary markets, mirroring earlier practices seen in mortgage securitization. Furthermore, property management firms have integrated energy efficiency upgrades into rent maximisation strategies, thereby transferring the costs of retrofitting onto tenants through increased rents or service charges²⁴. In some cases, smart metering technologies are used to monitor and regulate energy consumption, enabling more precise debt tracking

¹⁹ Holm, A., Alexandri, G., Bernt, M., 2023. *Housing Policy under the conditions of financialization. The impact of institutional investors on affordable housing in European Cities*, available at: <https://www.sciencespo.fr/ecole-urbaine/sites/sciencespo.fr/ecole-urbaine/files/RapportHousingHopofin.pdf>

²⁰ Ryan-Collins, J., 2021. Breaking the housing–finance cycle: Macroeconomic policy reforms for more affordable homes. *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space*, 53(3), pp.480-502.

²¹ Adkins, L., Cooper, M. & Konings, M., 2020 *op.cit.*

²² Byrne, M., 2020. Generation rent and the financialization of housing: A comparative exploration of the growth of the private rental sector in Ireland, the UK and Spain. *Housing Studies*, 35(4), pp.743-765.

²³ Adkins, L., Cooper, M. & Konings, M., 2020 *op.cit.*

²⁴ Dolores, L., Macchiaroli, M. & De Mare, G., 2022. "Financial Impacts of the Energy Transition in Housing", *Sustainability*, 14(9), pp.1-17.

and, in turn, facilitating the commodification of energy arrears²⁵. This dynamic illustrates how housing financialisation extends beyond property itself, incorporating essential services like energy into broader circuits of financial accumulation, thereby deepening household indebtedness and reinforcing socio-economic inequalities in the housing sector.

These structural forces have resulted in mounting housing and energy expenditures, spatial segregation, and a decline in social housing provision, disproportionately affecting lower-income and marginalised groups. Financial instruments such as mortgage securitisation and macroprudential regulations have had a substantial impact on housing access, frequently exacerbating socio-economic inequalities by augmenting household debt obligations and commodifying fundamental needs. It is therefore vital to investigate how Prototypes of Change navigate, resist, or adapt to these financial logics if viable policy recommendations and governance models that challenge dominant market paradigms are to be formulated. Moreover, the growing influence of private and institutional investors –fuelled by buy-to-let schemes and speculative investment practices– has intensified affordability crises, particularly in urban centres. This has had a significant impact on low-income households, many of whom have been compelled to enter into insecure rental arrangements or to seek refuge in peripheral areas with limited access to employment and essential services. In light of these challenges, the focus of PREFIGURE on Prototypes of Change is of paramount importance, as it aims to identify counter-strategies that prioritise housing affordability, long-term security, and sustainable urban development. By critically engaging with the financial mechanisms that underpin current housing and energy markets, PREFIGURE’s research contributes to the conceptualisation of and promotion of alternative models that have the potential to disrupt entrenched patterns of inequality and promote more resilient, inclusive forms of urban living.

By integrating a political economy approach, PREFIGURE ensures that its research is not only descriptive but also diagnostic, offering a critical lens through which to assess the systemic drivers of housing inequalities and the transformative potential of Prototypes of Change. This methodological approach enables a thorough evaluation of the potential for social innovation and alternative governance mechanisms to collaboratively transform the housing landscape towards greater equity and sustainability. The qualitative methods and political economy analytical framework employed by PREFIGURE provide critical tools with which to deconstruct the complex dynamics of housing financialisation and to evaluate how Prototypes of Change emerge as responses to both financialised housing markets and the increasing financialisation of energy systems. By examining the historical trajectories of housing and energy policies alongside market transformations, PREFIGURE can assess the structural conditions under which these prototypes not only arise but also have the potential to scale and influence broader systemic change. Situating these initiatives within the wider context of labour market precarity, generational wealth disparities, and evolving regulatory environments allows the research to illuminate the factors that enable or constrain their transformative capacity.

²⁵ Hernández, D. & Siegel, E., 2019. Energy insecurity and its ill health effects: a community perspective on the energy-health nexus in New York City. *Energy research & social science* 47, pp.78-83.

3.2 Insights from Urban Political Ecology

Urban Political Ecology (UPE) provides a critical analytical framework for understanding how socio-political, economic, and environmental factors intersect to produce housing and energy inequalities. UPE moves beyond technocratic and depoliticised narratives that frame housing and energy transitions as purely technical challenges. Instead, it foregrounds the entrenched power relations, governance structures, and socio-spatial dynamics that perpetuate energy poverty and environmental injustices. UPE reveals housing and energy systems as actively shaped by historical and contemporary struggles over resources, rights, and space, rather than as neutral or apolitical processes.

UPE's methodological approach is characterised by its emphasis on two key concepts: urban metabolic flows and embodied infrastructures. These concepts are instrumental in elucidating the material and social processes through which energy and housing resources circulate within urban environments²⁶. The analysis of these flows reveals the role of housing conditions, such as inadequate insulation, outdated heating systems, and overcrowded living spaces, in contributing to energy vulnerability. It is important to note that such vulnerabilities disproportionately affect low-income and marginalised communities. These communities are often relegated to energy-inefficient housing due to affordability constraints and systemic discrimination, thereby exacerbating both energy poverty and social exclusion²⁷. This intersection of environmental and social injustice underscores the necessity of addressing housing and energy transitions simultaneously, as isolated interventions risk reproducing existing inequalities.

Moreover, UPE provides a critical lens for interpreting social inequalities through the framework of energy rights and energy justice, emphasising how access to energy is deeply embedded within power relations, spatial injustices, and socio-economic hierarchies. Rather than perceiving energy poverty as an isolated technical issue, UPE underscores the political and structural processes that determine who has access to affordable, reliable, and sustainable energy, and who remains marginalised²⁸. The concept of justice within UPE extends beyond the mere distribution of energy resources to encompass questions of recognition, procedural justice, and the right to participate in decision-making processes that shape energy governance. This approach reveals how energy infrastructures are not neutral but are actively produced through historical patterns of urban development, capitalist accumulation, and environmental governance, which systematically disadvantage low-income communities, racialised groups, and peripheral urban areas²⁹. For example, austerity measures, neoliberal housing policies, and the privatization of energy systems often exacerbate energy precarity, as they prioritize profit over equitable access to basic services³⁰. UPE conceptualises energy

²⁶ Kennedy, C., Pincetl, S., & Bunje, P. (2011). The study of urban metabolism and its applications to urban planning and design. *Environmental Pollution*, 159(8-9), 1965–1973; Newell, J. P., & Cousins, J. J. (2015). The boundaries of urban metabolism: Towards a political-industrial ecology. *Progress in Human Geography*, 39(6), 702–728.

²⁷ Bouzarovski, S., & Petrova, S. (2015). A global perspective on domestic energy deprivation: Overcoming the energy poverty–fuel poverty binary. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 10, 31–40.

²⁸ Bulkeley, H., Edwards, G. A. S., & Fuller, S. (2014). Contesting climate justice in the city: Examining politics and practice in urban climate change experiments. *Global Environmental Change*, 25, 31–40. Bouzarovski, S., & Simcock, N. (2017). Spatializing energy justice. *Energy Policy*, 107, 640–648.

²⁹ Sovacool, B. K., Burke, M., Baker, L., Kotikalapudi, C. K., & Wlokas, H. (2017). New frontiers and conceptual frameworks for energy justice. *Energy Policy*, 105, 677–691.

³⁰ Bouzarovski, S. (2014). Energy poverty in the European Union: Landscapes of vulnerability. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Energy and Environment*, 3(3), 276–289.

justice not only as a matter of fair distribution but also as a broader struggle for social and environmental rights, thereby linking energy inequalities to wider issues of housing, urban citizenship, and environmental justice. This perspective underscores the importance of grassroots movements and community-led initiatives, such as Prototypes of Change, that contest these inequalities and advocate for energy as a fundamental right, rather than a market commodity.

The integration of UPE with Urban Political Economy perspectives is central to the investigation of how bottom-up innovations, termed Prototypes of Change, emerge in response to these structural inequalities. These prototypes represent community-led, sustainable housing and energy initiatives that not only aim to mitigate energy poverty but also to challenge the broader socio-political systems that engender such vulnerabilities. PREFIGURE's research critically examines three interrelated dimensions:

- **The Uneven Development of Urban Environments:** Investigating how neoliberal urban policies, housing privatisation, and financialised real estate markets have intensified housing and energy precarity, particularly in the context of austerity-driven governance and climate-related urban risks.
- **The Politics of Scale:** Analysing how governance structures at municipal, national, and supranational levels shape the distribution of energy-efficient housing and resources, and how grassroots movements navigate these scales to influence policy.
- **Environmental and Social Justice Claims:** Examining how grassroots organisations, social movements, and community-led Prototypes of Change mobilise to contest housing and energy inequalities, often reframing these issues as matters of environmental justice and the right to the city.

In this sense, the integration of insights from both Urban Political Economy and Urban Political Ecology provides a comprehensive framework for assessing the drivers, challenges, and upscaling potential of Prototypes of Change. This interdisciplinary approach enables PREFIGURE to offer policymakers, citizens, and market actors actionable insights into fostering just and sustainable housing and energy transitions. By critically examining how state policies at multiple governance scales intersect with environmental dynamics, PREFIGURE interrogates the structural forces that shape housing markets and energy accessibility. The subsequent section will examine PREFIGURE's contributions in detail, demonstrating how the project works to bridge disciplinary divides, expand the conceptual focus from poverty to precarity, and contest the limitations of techno-managerial approaches in addressing the intertwined crises of housing and energy.

4. Situating the Prototypes of Change within a Context of key Socio-Ecological Challenges

The conceptual framework delineated in the preceding section enables PREFIGURE to situate the specific case studies research of the Prototypes of Change within the context of two key challenges confronting European societies in their efforts to address housing and energy inequalities. The first challenge emanates from the siloed understanding of housing and energy as discrete concerns, a perspective profoundly entrenched in prevailing policy frameworks. The second challenge stems from decades of path dependency on solution and policy interventions rooted in the ecomodernist paradigm, which often limits transformative potential and social innovation. In the following sections, the manner in which PREFIGURE's research engages with these two key challenges will be demonstrated, as will the manner in which our research on Prototypes of Change can benefit policy-makers and citizens that struggle to address these challenges.

4.1 First Challenge: The Siloed Understanding of Housing and Energy

European societies are confronted with a dual and interconnected socio-environmental crisis. On the one hand, there is a deepening housing crisis, that is significantly reshaping the structural pillars of social cohesion³¹. Over the past decades, housing has become increasingly inaccessible and unaffordable for millions of people, not only for low-income, single-parent, ethnic minorities, refugees, and other non-privileged households and groups, but increasingly for the middle classes too³². On the other hand, a persistent energy crisis underlies the European green transition. Inflation, warfare and the sharp escalation in energy prices, particularly over the past five years, have further consolidated existing social vulnerabilities, exerting significant effects on low- and middle-income households.

Despite the common tendency to regard energy poverty and housing inequalities as discrete policy concerns, there is an increasing recognition of their interlinkages, which have resulted in a deepening socio-environmental crisis. Consequently, the relationship between housing and energy has been regarded as a nexus, with this dynamic now affecting all tenancy types. Both homeowners and tenants face distinct challenges related to paying rents, energy bills, and transitioning to greener futures. Moreover, homeowners and professional housing companies are grappling with significant financial constraints due to rising interest rates. For instance, the calls for rapid, large-scale renovation of existing housing stock in Europe to

³¹ Housing Europe, 2021. *The State of Housing in Europe 2021*, available at: <https://www.housingeurope.eu/resource-1705/the-state-of-housing-in-europe-2022>, accessed on 21/08/2022.

³² United Nations Special Rapporteur, 2018. *Access to justice for the right to housing*, A/HRC/40/61 accessed on 13/2/2020; Anacker, K.B., 2019. Introduction: Housing affordability and affordable housing. *International Journal of Housing Policy*, 19.1, pp.1-16.

achieve higher energy efficiency has become less profitable and more difficult to finance. In short, energy poverty and housing inequalities reinforce each other.

However, the current approach to discussing, researching and addressing energy and housing issues at European, national and local policy levels is fragmented, impeding the structural and institutional changes needed for a transition to more just socio-environmental futures³³. The European Green Deal, for instance, aims to tackle energy poverty and offers significant political and financial incentives for a green transition³⁴. Analogous initiatives such as the ‘Renovation Wave Strategy’ and the ‘Affordable Housing Initiative’ have been proposed as mechanisms to provide financial incentives for upgrading the housing stock and reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Nonetheless, these legislative tools have been subject to criticism due to their perceived inability to address the complex interplay between housing vulnerability and energy poverty. This compartmentalised approach, coupled with a path dependency on technological, financial, or managerial solutions (ecomodernisation), has been identified as a key impediment to achieving just transition outcomes. Moreover, growing evidence points to the exacerbation of existing housing inequalities and energy poverty by the emphasis on green transition through financial incentives and technological innovation in the energy, housing and real estate markets.

PREFIGURE emerged in response to this siloed political and economic context, driven by the need to promote a just energy transition in European cities and with a strong focus on addressing the interconnected challenges of energy and housing inequalities. In this regard, PREFIGURE’s pioneering contribution lies in its conceptualisation of energy poverty, expanding its traditional scope to encompass the intertwined forces of housing and energy precarity.

4.1.2 PREFIGURE’s first intervention: Expanding the Definition of ‘Energy Poverty’ to Address the Housing-Energy Precarity as an Interrelated Socio-Environmental Nexus

PREFIGURE argues that in order to overcome the compartmentalised analysis of socio-environmental issues and establish pathways towards just socio-environmental futures, it is imperative to institute a conceptual and methodological framework for addressing housing and energy as interrelated and interconnected socio-environmental issues.

Conceptually, PREFIGURE contends that it is essential to broaden our definition of energy poverty to encompass housing conditions and the evolving housing and tenancy systems across Europe³⁵ in the aftermath of the 2008 economic crisis³⁶. To achieve this objective, PREFIGURE combines political economy approaches that explore the consequences of housing inequalities with research methodologies examining energy as a social relation, grounded in urban political ecology³⁷. The connection between urban political ecology and housing

³³ European Commission, 2020. A strategy for smart, sustainable, and inclusive growth, available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52010DC2020>, accessed on 21/09/2022.

³⁴ European Commission, 2020. Renovation Wave for Europe - greening our buildings, creating jobs, improving lives, available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1603122220757&uri=CELEX:52020DC0662>, accessed on 2/5/2021.

³⁵ Blackwell, T. & Kohl, S., 2018. The origins of national housing finance systems: a comparative investigation into historical variations in mortgage finance regimes. *Review of International Political Economy*, 25.1: 49-74.

³⁶ Schwartz, H.M. & Seabrooke, L., 2009. Varieties of residential capitalism in the international political economy: Old welfare states and the new politics of housing. In Schwartz, H.M. and Seabrooke, L. (eds) *The politics of housing booms and busts*. London: Palgrave Macmillan:1-27.

³⁷ Kaika, M., Keil, R., Mandler, T., & Tzaninis, Y. (2023). *Turning up the heat: urban political ecology for a climate emergency*. doi:10.7765/9781526168016

inequalities is twofold: both focus on how power, politics and socio-environmental factors shape urban life. This approach recognises housing inequalities as not just an economic but also a deeply environmental and political issue. This approach for PREFIGURE is designed to offer a more nuanced understanding of the interplay between socio-economic relations, socio-spatial conditions, and socio-natural processes that contribute to housing inequalities, energy poverty, and energy vulnerability. Achieving this objective will require significant breakthroughs in the conceptualisation and policymaking related to sustainable housing and energy transitions. A core component of these breakthroughs will be a reconceptualisation of energy poverty itself.

The prevailing definition of energy poverty in EU policies encompasses inadequate access to energy supplies³⁸, the inability of households to adequately heat living spaces, delays in paying utility bills, and residing in defective dwellings with issues such as leaky roofs, damaged walls or foundations, mould, or rot. This definition gives rise to concerns related to social exclusion, material deprivation and poor health³⁹, economic, infrastructural, social equity, educational, and health-related concerns. However, this definition does not entail the relation between energy poverty and housing precarity or the increasing challenges faced by households in meeting their energy bills due to rising mortgage repayments in the context of housing financialisation.

In summary, while energy poverty and housing precarity individually receive significant policy and research attention, this focus remains constrained by siloed understandings that treat housing and energy poverty as separate issues. Consequently, the emphasis on energy poverty, as implemented in policy-making, obscures as much as it reveals. PREFIGURE maintains that revising the concepts employed in policy-making is not merely a theoretical academic exercise. Ultimately, the project aspires to have a tangible impact by transcending the academic realm and entering the policy domain, striving to ensure that research informs policy rather than policy dictating research.

To illustrate this conceptualisation, we provide an example from the Netherlands. According to the current definition of energy poverty, which considers a combination of high energy costs, inadequate insulation, and low income, approximately 7% of Dutch households were classified as energy poor in 2019⁴⁰. However, if the concept of energy poverty is expanded to encompass not only the affordability of energy, but also the energy efficiency of houses and households' ability to participate in the energy transition (which is related to household obligations to access housing), the percentage of energy-poor households would increase exponentially to 48%.⁴¹

The findings in the Netherlands can be extrapolated to most European countries. The inability to participate in the energy transition due to energy poverty affects millions of tenants and

³⁸ Bouzarovski, S., Petrova, S. & Tirado-Herrero, S., 2014. From Fuel Poverty to Energy Vulnerability: The Importance of Services, Needs and Practices. SPRU Science Policy Research Unit. University of Sussex. *Working Paper Series SWPS* 2014-25

³⁹ Hilbert, A. & Werner, M., 2016. Turn up the heat! Contesting energy poverty in Buffalo, NY. *Geoforum*, 74: 222-232.; Castaño-Rosa, R., Solís-Guzmán, J., Rubio-Bellido, C. & Marrero, M., 2019. Towards a multiple-indicator approach to energy poverty in the European Union: A review. *Energy and Buildings*, 193: 36-48.

⁴⁰ Mulder, L., Koster, A., Wouters, A., Peerdeman, S., Croiset, G., Ravesloot, J., Akwivu, E., Salih, M., & Kusrkar, R. 2023. Diversity in the pathway from med stud to specialist in the Netherlands. *The Lancet Regional Health - Europe*. 35. 100749.10.1016/j.lanepe.2023.100749.

⁴¹ Mulder, P., Dalla Longa, F., & Straver, K. (2023). Energy poverty in the Netherlands at the national and local level: A multi-dimensional spatial analysis. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 96, 102892. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102892>

owners-occupiers who lack enough capital or have mortgage debts. In its 2019 Environmental Law, the Netherlands addressed energy poverty not as a standalone issue, but as part of broader income poverty and distribution issues⁴². This approach, although not aligned with the EU toolkit of concepts, did nevertheless allude to the fact that energy poverty cannot be addressed as a separate, insular problem; it needs to be contextualised in relation to housing and income inequalities. However, in 2019 the EU issued a warning against the Dutch government for failing to address energy poverty (in its current narrow definition) explicitly as part of the country's energy transition programme⁴³. If policy is narrowly focused on energy poverty, ignoring housing precarity and mortgage precarity, it will be ineffective in addressing the social, environmental, and economic issues faced by a significant proportion of the population, especially in the context of the demand for green energy transitions. Indeed, across the EU, low-income homeowners and middle-income homeowners with substantial mortgages are in a vulnerable position⁴⁴, even though the public debate often focuses primarily on the position of the social housing tenants when discussing energy poverty.

In short, when we start exploring housing and energy in tandem, we reveal an almost counter-intuitive truth: it is not energy poverty as such, but the relationship between energy poverty and housing inequality that lies at the core of the inability to advance toward just energy transitions. Therefore, one of PREFIGURE's key objectives is to revise current conceptual working definitions and frameworks, to highlight how closely energy poverty is linked to the political economy of the housing markets, particularly the financialisation of housing.

PREFIGURE conducts a comparative analysis of housing and energy inequalities across seven European countries, complemented by local case studies (Prototypes of Change). The project generates unique qualitative and quantitative evidence on the nexus between housing inequalities, energy poverty, income and wealth polarisation, and the socio-spatial impacts of sustainable housing and energy transitions. The central argument is that the strong link between servicing mortgage payments, managing energy bills, and upgrading housing stock should be central to discussions on energy transitions, yet this relationship remains obscured by narrow definitions of energy poverty.

As the first empirical research programme to provide clear, measurable indicators of the uneven effects of energy transition demands amidst rising housing instability and financialisation, PREFIGURE examines how diverse stakeholders, differentiated by ownership and tenure, pursue housing energy efficiency strategies. The project is critical in its evaluation of housing and energy systems, identifying emerging patterns of socio-spatial segregation and investigating the unequal distribution of financial benefits from transition incentives between homeowners, tenants, and financial actors with greater capacity to invest in and manage energetic refurbishments.

A key contribution of PREFIGURE is its intersectional approach, integrating feminist political ecology, critical geography, and urban political economy to explore how gender, class, ethnic-

⁴² The Dutch 2019 Climate Law 'to reduce greenhouse emissions in The Netherlands by 49% in 2030 (Salet, 2021, p.6) did not recognize energy poverty as a problem per se

⁴³ Feenstra, M., Middlemiss, L., Hesselman, M., Straver, K., & Tirado Herrero, S. 2021. Humanising the Energy Transition: Towards a National Policy on Energy Poverty in the Netherlands. *Frontiers in Sustainable Cities*, 3, 1-11. Article 645624. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsc.2021.645624>

⁴⁴ García Lamarca, M., & Kaika, M. (2016). „Mortgaged Lives“: the biopolitics of debt and housing financialisation *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers*. DOI: 10.1111/tran.12126, 41(3), 313-327. doi:10.1111/tran.12126

ity, and culture shape access to housing and energy resources. Research on housing and energy poverty often neglects the embodied, emotional, and everyday experiences of those at the intersection of multiple disadvantages. PREFIGURE addresses this gap by foregrounding the lived realities of marginalised groups. For instance, women-led single-parent households face disproportionate energy poverty due to wage disparities, unpaid care responsibilities, and reliance on social housing, while ethnic minorities and refugees are more likely to experience inadequate housing due to discriminatory rental markets and precarious labour conditions. By centring these perspectives, the project deepens understanding of housing-energy dynamics and informs policy recommendations that prioritise equity and inclusion.

4.2 Second Challenge: Path Dependency on Ecomodernist Techno-Managerial Solutions

Alongside the siloed comprehension of housing and energy precarity, a further obstacle obstructs the execution of radical interventions imperative for achieving just transitions: policy-makers adherence to the ecomodernisation paradigm, which perceives financial or techno-managerial solutions as the sole instruments for addressing socio-ecological challenges. Since the Brundtland report, ecomodernism has become the pillar of EU environmental legislation, promoting two key methods for delivering sustainable futures: financial incentives and techno-managerial innovations. However, these approaches have consistently proven inefficient, as they tend to shift problems rather than deliver meaningful, transformative change.

For instance, since the 1990s, the EU's approach to water resource management has been to consider it a technical, managerial, or fiscal issue, resulting in policies that have promoted, financed, and at times demanded (during the 2008 crisis) a series of water privatisation programmes. This practice has been similarly promoted across the world by the IMF and the World Bank. However, these privatisation programmes have dismally failed to deliver better or fairer water management⁴⁵. In addressing the nexus of housing inequality and energy poverty during periods of transition, it is essential to draw from the lessons of past failures of the eco-modernist paradigm in water infrastructure management. This knowledge can and should inform the planning of just energy transitions.

In summary, it is insufficient to merely transcend siloed understandings; it is imperative to modify our research methodologies and policy instruments, and to move beyond the confines of the ecomodernist paradigm to address the pressing housing and energy crises confronting Europe in the present context of transition. This necessitates a shift not only in the fundamental concepts with which we are engaged but also to refine our methods and, more crucially, the *interlocutors* with whom we engage. Moreover, it is crucial to expand the scope of our interaction to encompass a more diverse range of stakeholders, including communities, who can offer valuable insights into innovative approaches.

Hence, PREFIGURE's second innovation lies in the identification, documentation, and utilisation of the transformative capacity of alternative innovative initiatives for community-based or driven knowledge and technology creation that go beyond top-down or market-driven techno-

⁴⁵ Kishimoto, S. & Olivier P. 2017. "Introduction: The untold story". In *Reclaiming Public Services: How cities and citizens are turning back privatization*. Edited by Satoko Kishimoto, Olivier Petitjean and Lavinia Steinfort. 2017. Amsterdam and Paris: Transnational Institute (TNI), Multinationals Observatory, Austrian Federal Chamber of Labour (AK), European Federation of Public Service Unions (EPSU), and others. June, pp. 11-23. www.tni.org/reclaiming-public-services.

managerial solutions.

4.2.2 PREFIGURE's Second Intervention: Prototypes of Change Documenting and Harnessing the Transformative Capacity of Bottom-up Action for Knowledge Creation beyond Techno-Managerial Solutions

In the context of the social, political, and economic challenges outlined above, PREFIGURE examines existing and emerging collective efforts (bottom-up and participatory approaches) that actively produce alternative and innovative models, therefore initiating a more just and sustainable housing and energy transition. PREFIGURE is among the first international comparative research projects to identify, analyse, and connect such initiatives, which are termed "Prototypes of Change". These prototypes represent practices that not only address the intersection of housing and energy poverty, but also transcend the limitations of siloed understandings by creating methods that go beyond techno-managerial or fiscal solutions. These prototypes embody diverse social, political, and economic practices designed to foster innovation, support affordable housing renovation, and develop solutions to reduce housing inequalities, particularly benefiting vulnerable households and communities.

PREFIGURE systematically researches, assesses, and typifies the modes and mechanisms of such bottom-up approaches and initiatives that address the Housing-Energy Nexus, and evaluates the potential for scaling up and cross-fertilising these efforts. PREFIGURE draws attention to these locally grounded practices of innovation –whether entirely bottom-up or in co-operation with institutions– because of their capacity to drive the green transition in ways that more effectively address existing inequalities. By leveraging the knowledge and expertise stemming from these innovative practices, and drawing insights from the Prototypes of Change towards a just transition, PREFIGURE seeks to extrapolate, upscale and adapt these innovations in transferable ways for different contexts.

PREFIGURE places emphasis on practices of transformative social innovation, which often emerge locally in specific places and socio-cultural environments in the form of community or grassroots initiatives. This focus on bottom-up and 'out of the box' practices of innovation that respond to the housing and energy crisis comprehends different social, socio-technical, and socio-environmental innovations led by communities, organised civic initiatives, institutional and market actors, offering alternative policy and economic responses⁴⁶. Academic discourse on such transformative social innovation refers to them as a bottom-up process aiming at resisting and reverting social exclusion and contributing to the empowerment of disadvantaged groups by addressing social cohesion. In this regard, transformative innovation meets the needs of society which are overlooked by the mainstream economy and the state, and changes social relations. The term 'social' in this context denotes the value type that innovations are expected to deliver, with a focus on quality of life, solidarity, and well-being, as opposed to profit and market efficiency⁴⁷.

Such emerging initiatives in different fields of the so-called social and solidarity economy or

⁴⁶ Academic discourse on such transformative social innovation refers to them as a bottom-linked process aiming at resisting and reverting social exclusion and contributing to empowerment (of disadvantaged groups) by addressing social cohesion.

⁴⁷ Galdini, R. & Lucciarini, S., 2019. Social innovation and environmental sustainability in social housing policies: Learning from two experimental case studies in Italy. In Cakmakli, A. ed. *Different Strategies of Housing Design*. London: InTechOpen: 63-82.

'diverse economies'⁴⁸, have been widely discussed in the aftermath of the 2008 financial and economic crisis⁴⁹, and have also been the focus of some EU Horizon projects⁵⁰. In the context of sustainable housing and energy transitions, the PREFIGURE project is noteworthy for its unique approach in integrating both approaches. It aims to facilitate co-creation and joint exploration with citizens and other stakeholders on the potential for societal transformation. To this end, the project undertakes a comprehensive identification, tracking, networking, and comparative analysis of local initiatives concerning housing and energy transitions. It also establishes transnational dialogues to support the co-creation and practical implementation of affordable housing policy actions.

⁴⁸ Gibson-Graham, J.K., 2008. Diverse economies: performative practices for other worlds. *Progress in Human Geography* 32.5: 613-632; Gibson-Graham JK & Dombroski K, 2020. Introduction to *The Handbook of Diverse Economies: inventory as ethical intervention*. In *The handbook of diverse economies*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing.

⁴⁹ Gritzas, G., & Kavoulakos, K. I. (2016). Diverse economies and alternative spaces: An overview of approaches and practices. *European Urban and Regional Studies*, 23(4), 917-934. doi:10.1177/0969776415573778

⁵⁰ <https://www.socialeconomy.eu.org/our-work/projects-2/>

5. Identifying and Selecting Prototypes of Change as Case Studies

Mobilising the insights from Urban Political Ecology and Political Economy, and in relation to the two key challenges outlined in the previous sections, the project partners carefully selected the case study localities in which the prototypes operate, based on their exposure to different relevant aspects that impact their potential for sustainable housing and energy transitions. These aspects include: housing tenure systems (i.e., owner occupier rates), housing deprivation rates, recent changes in building energy efficiency, and absolute values of household energy consumption. It is noted that all these factors vary widely across Europe and across the case countries. Additionally, the composition of housing inequalities, wealth and income polarisation, and the evolving nature of housing policies and real estate markets over the past few decades also differ significantly between countries and cities.

In selecting case studies, a concerted effort was made to ensure representation of a diverse range of socio-political and economic contexts, as well as geographic regions across the European Union. The selection of Germany, the Netherlands, the UK, Denmark, Spain, Greece, Estonia, and Bulgaria as the case countries reflects the necessity of encompassing different poles and types of diversity necessary for a comprehensive overview. The local study cases also vary in size and complexity, and while they include larger capital cities, they are not limited to them. Specifically, local study cases include Karlsruhe (DE), Amsterdam (NL), Burgas (BG), Gabrovo (BG), Tallinn (EE), Barcelona (ES), Thessaloniki (GR), Copenhagen (DK) London (UK), and Ioannina (GR). All partners conducted research within local, regional and national environments where they were already embedded leveraging their expertise, networks and capacity for longitudinal ethnographic research in energy and/or housing. This methodological approach enabled the team to effectively carry out bidirectional socio-technical action research and other participatory approaches facilitating the successful co-creation of knowledge and policy.

The broad range of localities and contexts of urban governance presents a unique and valuable opportunity for research and policy development. Building on Robinson's assertions, PREFIGURE aims to employ a relational comparative approach that examines diversity and differences by analysing localities through the lens of each other⁵¹. Recognising the limitations of directly applying theories from one context to another, the project partners aspire to foster an analysis that not only acknowledges differences but also uses them to think with and beyond distinctions, allowing one place to be understood through the perspective of another. While the impacts of housing financialisation and energy poverty are evident in all the cities chosen as prototypes, the cases differ significantly in their housing markets, urban

⁵¹ Robinson, J. (2022). *Comparative Urbanism: Tactics for Global Urban Studies*. New York: Wiley.

and energy policies, and regulations, the interplay between local and national governments, and their historical urbanisation trajectories. In this sense, the methodology underscores the significance of the researcher's positionality and the need to develop tailored tools and strategies for data collection and analysis. The potential of this comparison is such that it can ultimately provide a broader perspective on concepts such as housing financialisation, energy poverty, energy transition, deal-making/state informality, and state-society relations. These insights would have been less attainable if the focus had been limited to a single locality. The cognitive dissonance experienced by urban researchers when encountering new contexts encourages innovative thinking in comparative studies⁵². In the subsequent phases of PREFIGURE, researchers and collaborators intend to implement specific methodologies, including facilitating interaction among case studies and tracing the dissemination of ideas, policies, and human mobility across different localities. This comparative analysis will be further elaborated in subsequent reports.

6. Research Questions and Guidelines for Comparative Research on Prototypes

Following the selection of case studies based on the previously outlined criteria, PREFIGURE developed a common framework with key research questions and methods that were consistent across all research teams and case studies. This step was of paramount importance in establishing a uniform research framework (questions and methods) on which a comparative analysis would be conducted at the project's subsequent stages. When deemed necessary, modifications were made to the methods for each case study. Subsequently, the common research questions that drove the ethnographic and qualitative research into each case study prototype will be presented. Each team adapted these questions into an *interview guide* for conducting expert, in-depth, narrative, or biographic interviews. Depending on the specific methods applied in the field and the timing of the research, each team recognised the need to adapt these research questions to their context.

The research questions were formulated around five key themes, namely the history and evolution of the Prototype of Change, the internal governance, the role of technology, the type of innovation, and the potential future challenges. Regarding the history, foundation and the evolution of the prototype, the concrete research questions focused on tracing the inception, development, and impact of the prototype over time, and on identifying the initial motivations behind the prototype, as well as the actors responsible for its initiation. A key area of inquiry was set around the primary challenge the prototype aimed to address, particularly in relation to energy and housing policies. The study also examined whether its creation was driven by specific policy changes and how it sought to respond to pressing social, economic, or environmental needs. In addition, the research examined the role of property regimes and housing systems, analysing how these structures influenced the development of the prototype and, conversely, how the prototype itself may have contributed to shaping housing systems and property dynamics.

⁵² Brill, F. (2022) Practising comparative urbanism: Methods and consequences. *Area*, 54, 252–259.

Moreover, the research examined the internal governance structures of each prototype, analysing their organisational frameworks and decision-making processes. In addition, it also explored the ownership status of the infrastructure on which the prototypes operate, shedding light on property relations and access to housing and energy. A further key focus was on the financial resources supporting each prototype, exploring whether these are self-funded, subsidised, or reliant on alternative economic structures. Additionally, the research considered internal discords and the challenges that arise in internal governance structures, providing insights into the complexities of sustaining such initiatives over time.

Further research questions investigated the interplay between technology, infrastructure, and policy in shaping the development and impact of each prototype, highlighting the ways in which technological advancements, regulatory frameworks, and infrastructural conditions influenced the potential success. The research also explored the role of technology and policy in broader socio-economic and environmental transitions, analysing their potential to drive or obstruct systemic change. By assessing these factors, the data collection aimed to provide a deeper understanding of the structural opportunities and constraints that shape the evolution of such initiatives.

In this sense, PREFIGURE examined the innovative aspects of each prototype, investigating whether its contributions lay in the realm of housing, energy, or both. It explored the motivations behind focusing on one domain over the other and whether participants had considered the interconnections between housing and energy systems. A key focus was on how the prototype addressed the nexus of energy and housing precarity in ways that differed from conventional policies and practices at both local and national levels. Research questions sought to identify the key drivers of innovation, including community involvement, technological advancements, ownership models, infrastructure conditions, financial structures, and labour relations. Furthermore, it examined whether the innovation led to more equitable access to housing and energy, analysing the factors that enabled such inclusivity—such as collective ownership of housing or infrastructure. By unpacking these dynamics, the study provided insights into how alternative models could challenge existing systems and create pathways toward more just and sustainable living conditions.

Finally, the research questions addressed the future challenges encountered by the prototype, assessing its success, shortcomings, and the lessons learned from past mistakes. It assessed the feasibility of continuing the initiative, considering financial sustainability, community capacity, legal constraints, and other key factors that could influence its longevity. Our research also explored the question of scalability, analysing whether expanding the prototype was desirable and, if so, how it could be achieved. This included an examination of potential funding sources, necessary labour contributions, and the connections required to support growth. By addressing these aspects, the conducted empirical research provided a comprehensive understanding of both the obstacles and opportunities that shaped the trajectory of each prototype.

7. Methodology for Comparative Research on Prototypes

PREFIGURE reflects recent epistemological shifts in the broader field of social sciences, especially at the intersection of sustainability research, critical urban studies, and planning. In this sense, PREFIGURE has initiated the establishment of mechanisms for bidirectional and collaborative knowledge transfer, with the formation and consolidation of transdisciplinary learning communities being a central aspect of its epistemic comprehension⁵³. Engaging with sustainable housing and energy transitions, however, necessitates an emphasis on the emancipatory capacities underpinning transformative and prefigurative research, and its associated participatory research approach, which emerges from academic reflection and active involvement. This approach is characterised by co-production and co-creation of knowledge systems that address sustainable housing and energy transitions, resulting in multiple processes unfolding in cities. Citizens and urban stakeholders adapt existing resources to fit their needs, reclaim underutilised assets to meet their goals, and diversify planning practices to include broader interests, particularly those of marginalised and vulnerable communities. They challenge institutional boundaries by introducing alternative policy approaches and innovations that drive institutional change. Additionally, they expose power dynamics by reinterpreting and making resources more accessible to wider communities. Finally, they contest dominant narratives by actively challenging prevailing frameworks and traditional understandings of social and political transformation. This bottom-up understanding of disruption has led to the development of a methodological approach that uses Prototypes of Change. PREFIGURE aims to apply this to improve the lives of urban citizens.

To achieve this, all partners followed a common roadmap to gather comparable data and information, which was further adjusted to accommodate the specific local and urban characteristics of their local prototype. To gain a comprehensive understanding of the local context, partners have examined the underlying mechanisms influencing the specific case studies, focusing on historical, spatial, and legal contexts, as well as economic changes. This broad framework integrates economic, social, and political dynamics across various geographic scales and over extended historical timelines.

Analysing the development of housing and energy policies and the emergence of energy poverty in each case study necessitates a comprehensive perspective incorporating economic transformations, historical context, and geospatial aspects. To enhance this analysis, a policy

⁵³ Fazey, I. et al., (2013). Knowledge exchange: a review and research agenda for environmental management. *Env. Conservation* 40(1), pp.19-36; Ward, V. (2017): Why, whose, what and how? A framework for knowledge mobilisers. *Evidence & Policy* 13(3), pp.477-497; Koch, F. et al. (2017): A transformative turn towards sustainability in the context of urban-related studies? A systematic review from 1957 to 2016. *Sustainability* 10(1), 58; Haarstad, H., et al., (2018). Transformative social science? Modes of engagement in climate and energy solutions. *Energy Research & Social Science* 42, pp. 193-197.

trajectory approach has been employed to explore the evolution of housing and energy policies, legislative changes, and urban political dynamics. This method emphasises examining issues of interest, conflict, and power, highlighting shifts in power within contested spaces as critical components of the policymaking process. It is through this methodological approach that a comprehensive and coherent comparison can be fostered.

All teams employed a set of common qualitative methods to approach the prototypes and began fostering a learning community with people involved in the prototypes, who will commit to more intense and long-term engagement with PREFIGURE. They will become part of PREFIGURE's 'learning community' and act as 'ambassadors of change'. This includes participation in PREFIGURE's planned international exchanges, workshops and mobile laboratories that will foster co-creation and knowledge sharing between the prototype holders. The 'must-use' methods outlined below were complemented by 'additional' methods that some teams selected for use, with the understanding that the exact application of each method for each case study may vary and can include further, more experimental approaches and methods. In detail, the following methods were suggested to all partners, considering a comprehensive rationale to unify research methods within case-sensitive diversity, following specific rationales:

- **Document analysis** provides valuable insights through existing reports, public information, media information and social media engagement. This approach enables researchers to reconstruct the evolution and discourse about the prototype, examining historical data, policy documents, project reports, online sources, and other relevant materials to understand the prototype's background, goals, and outcomes. By analysing these documents, researchers identify patterns, track progress, and evaluate the effectiveness of the locally implemented strategies. Document analysis also facilitates cross-verification of information obtained through other methods, as well as academic and grey literature, thereby ensuring a comprehensive and accurate understanding of the prototype's impact and challenges.
- **Expert interviews** provide insights and specialised knowledge from individuals with first-hand experience and expertise in the wider social and political field surrounding the prototype. The engagement with experts enables researchers to obtain nuanced perspectives on the evolution of the prototype, its effectiveness, the socio-economic factors involved, and the practical challenges encountered. These interviews can reveal critical information that might not be evident through alternative research methods. Furthermore, the utilisation of expert interviews can assist in validating findings, offering a more comprehensive and credible analysis of the prototype, and guiding future research and policy recommendations. Additionally, they facilitate the establishment of personal connections with individuals central to the field surrounding the prototype, thereby fostering the development of a learning community.
- **Snowballing**, a technique of building upon insights gained through interviews, is employed at the end of each interview, and communication with all informants. This involves inquiring as to other potential interviewees who might contribute valuable insights and requesting their contact information and permission to contact them. They also help to bond personally with core persons in the field surrounding the prototype thus advancing

the creation of a learning community.

- **Narrative interviews** with crucial community actors including residents, neighbours and directly involved people with the evolution of the prototype support in-depth insights into the specific local trajectories. Narrative interviews aim at creating a constructive conversational atmosphere prone to capture personal insights and practices of those dealing in everyday life with the prototype.
- **Ethnographic observation** of the daily activities taking place in the environment of each prototype allows researchers to gather first-hand data and understand its real-life impact. By observing and participating in diverse activities, researchers can capture the nuances of how the prototype operates, the challenges faced by local communities, and the effectiveness of the employed strategies. This direct insight helps in identifying gaps, and developing a comprehensive understanding of the social dynamics and needs.
- **Collection of photographic and other visual materials** capture the living conditions and changes brought about by the prototype in a way that text alone cannot convey. This approach serves to document the context and environment, thereby rendering the research more engaging for a broader audience. Moreover, the analysis of visual materials can reveal aspects of the prototype that might be overlooked in written reports. The method offers a more holistic understanding of the prototype's effectiveness and areas for improvement. It is crucial to note that all visual material collection and publication adhere to the standard academic ethics guidelines; i.e. no faces or personal data and information should be presented or published without explicit consent.
- **Focus groups and other workshop formats** are tools to explore collaboratively the strengths and pitfalls of a prototype. While the preparation is extensive and time-consuming, the results allow deducing group-specific discourse on each prototype and pursuing an in-depth elaboration of how to further shape and transform the prototype.

8. Analysis of 12 Prototypes of Change: Overview and First Results

Empirical qualitative research on each prototype was initiated by the PREFIGURE partners in July 2024. This phase was characterised by the acquisition of profound insight from a diverse range of stakeholders, including community members, experts, academics, and policymakers, regarding their perceptions of the prototype’s potential role in facilitating collective transitions towards more energy-efficient and equitable societies. The research involved the conduction of 226 interviews over a six-month period, encompassing 12 Prototypes of Change. In addition to these interviews, more than 10 focus group discussions were held, alongside numerous workshops and extensive participant observation, and a significant volume of photographic documentation was collected.

The following sections present an in-depth analysis of aims objectives etc. as well as details on the fieldwork conducted for each prototype until January 2025. A more detailed comparative analysis and typology of the prototypes will be part of the subsequent report, Deliverable 2.2 - the Prototype Catalogue, once all fieldwork has been completed. However, a preliminary classification of the prototypes into four key categories has been undertaken, based on the primary actors driving the innovation, ownership of infrastructure and the means of production:

- The first of these is “Commoning”, defined as bottom-up co-production initiatives aiming at achieving structural changes in the ownership of infrastructures and the means of production, with the benefits being open and shared beyond the immediate community involved.
- The second is “Community”, defined as bottom-up co-production initiatives aiming at achieving institutional or technological changes without aiming for ownership of infrastructure or means of production, with the community not receiving monetary benefits or profit from these efforts.
- The third is “Social Entrepreneurship/Cooperative” defined as profit-seeking, bottom-up co-production initiatives that aim to develop new, community-owned infrastructures. The benefits, including any monetary income or profit, directly accrue to the actors involved, and do not extend to those who do not participate in the scheme.
- The fourth is model “Institution Driven Participatory”, which includes participation of market actors. It is characterised by top-down processes initiated by local planning authorities (in most cases), albeit with strong elements of deliberative democracy that extend standard participatory approaches. This model may include decision-making power for commu-

nities regarding key issues of management and/or ownership of infrastructures, and can involve market actors in some cases.

This typology provides a conceptual framework for the subsequent analysis and in-depth presentation of the 12 Prototypes of Change that were researched in the framework of the PREFIGURE project.

Thessaloniki

Commoning

8.1. Prototype 1. Refugee squats and self-housing (Thessaloniki GR – UVA)

Short Description (who initiated, aims and focus, type of prototype)

This research examines the practices of social innovation developed by refugees in state-run camps within the Thessaloniki region and by self-managed newcomer housing occupations in the city. It aims to explore practical solutions to improve living conditions –particularly housing and energy access– for populations often socially and spatially excluded from urban life and marginalized in society.

Following the closure of the Balkan route and the EU-Turkey agreement in March 2016, the Greek government established several state-run refugee camps in the Thessaloniki area to accommodate the influx of refugees. Refugees are confronted with substandard living conditions as they are housed in 27m² white isobox containers, each accommodating six to eight individuals. These prefabricated units, positioned on concrete rails, create a void underneath that often fills with stagnant water, fostering contamination and attracting mosquitoes, rodents, and snakes during warmer months. Each container is divided into two rooms with a small central kitchen and toilet, though poor construction results in inadequate drainage, leading to mould growth on the walls. Structural deterioration is evident, with rotting and cracked novopan flooring creating holes, and thin polyester walls (less than 10 cm thick) showing significant wear. This inadequate infrastructure highlights the health and safety risks faced by refugees in these state-run camps. On the

other hand, newcomers/ refugees in Thessaloniki are forced to reside in deteriorated, occupied buildings lacking basic infrastructure like windows, doors, electricity, and running water. These conditions expose residents to harsh weather and pests, forcing them to rely on candles, flashlights, and occasional fires for warmth. Fear of detection by authorities discourages visible heating methods. Overall, squatting in these buildings offers severe hardships and insecurity.

This research aims to examine the daily social innovation practices adopted by the refugee population to cope with and overcome inadequate living conditions, with a focus on housing and energy access. It also seeks to explore the potential for developing sustainable and energy-efficient solutions that can enhance overall living standards.

How does it address the Housing Energy Nexus (Green Energy, poverty, household type, tenancy)

State-run camps like CAFTAAS, in their current form, provide only basic living conditions and fail to serve as models for affordable and sustainable housing. This spatial and built environment of low-quality container housing in locations far

Summary table	Prototype of change
Name	Newcomers' Right to Energy in State-Run Refugee Camps + Self-Managed Energy Practices in Newcomers' Squats
Location	Thessaloniki
Type of Prototype	Vulnerability and Commoning
Focus	Refugee population and housing
Beneficiaries	Refugee population and vulnerable (marginal) social groups
Key Innovation	Social innovation, commoning & energy independence
Key outcomes	Social inclusion, housing, energy and social justice

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beyond the city core, limits residents' access to equitable housing and energy solutions and hinders the development of energy-efficient practices. In contrast, refugees living in occupied buildings face severe structural challenges, such as deteriorated infrastructure lacking windows, doors, and proper insulation. Despite these hardships, long-term squatting residents, particularly in Thessaloniki's Ano Poli area, actively improve their living conditions through self-managed repairs and improvised energy solutions, including informal utility connections, car battery energy generation, and makeshift gas stoves. These communities demonstrate strong solidarity through energy-sharing and cooperative practices,

reflecting grassroots social innovation aimed at overcoming substandard housing and energy insecurity.

Outcomes (Social, energetic, political)

The potential for green energy transitions in state-run camps largely depends on the policies of the Ministry of Migration and Asylum, which currently lacks a coherent strategy, administrative capacity and sufficient financial resources for

effective implementation. Proposed interventions include installing photovoltaic and rooftop solar panels on housing containers, utilizing wind and geothermal energy, implementing rainwater harvesting systems, and promoting gardening and bioclimatic design. Replacing outdated, poorly insulated containers with higher-quality units or constructing more permanent, thermally efficient structures could significantly improve living conditions, besides addressing the right to housing. Additionally, the integration of smart technologies

could enhance energy efficiency and resource management within the camps.

In contrast, occupied houses offer opportunities to strengthen solidarity and communal energy management among residents in collective housing arrangements. While squatters already engage in mutual support, financial constraints and uncertainty about their future hinder the adoption of long-term and advanced energy solutions. Targeted initiatives could focus on transforming abandoned warehouses in Thessaloniki's western areas into municipal shelters using bioclimatic and sustainable construction methods, operating independently of state migration policies under a model of

Fieldwork conducted to-date: Refugee squats and self-housing (Thessaloniki GR – UVA)

As part of the research, interviews were conducted with: a) 15 newcomers living in squatted houses – abandoned buildings in Thessaloniki; b) 25 residents (asylum seekers) of state-run camps (CAFTAAS); c) four managers of the state-run camps under examination (Vagiohori, Lagadikia, Polikastro, and Alexandria); and d) officials from the Ministry of Migration and Asylum, including the Reception and Identification Service, the Directorate of Structures, and the Head of the Technical Support Department.

Additionally, four workshops –focus groups involving 20-50 participants each– were held in the state-run camps with asylum seekers. During these workshops, participants used markers and drawing pads to depict methods of energy supply, energy devices, and how they cook their food both in their countries of origin and in the housing units (containers) within the state-run camps.

Field research also included on-site observations, visits to the state-run camps and squatted buildings, and informal discussions with NGO employees working in the camps. Furthermore, approximately 100 pages of personal notes and a diary were maintained from June 2024 to January 2025.

“municipal citizenship.” Partnerships with solidarity organizations and energy communities could provide squat residents with the technical expertise and sustainable energy solutions –such as small-scale photovoltaic systems, heat pumps, or wind turbines– necessary to enhance energy autonomy and resilience.

Upscaling (replication, expansion, institutional effects)

This research highlights a critical gap in national and European policies regarding the integration of green and renewable energy solutions in housing for asylum seekers and refugees, particularly within state-run camps like CAFTAAS. Implementing pilot projects for energy upgrades in these camps could generate significant local impact and serve as scalable models for broader national and European adoption. Such initiatives could contribute to forming a new institutional framework that simultaneously addresses energy efficiency and refugee housing needs, promotes the use of renewable energy sources, encourages participatory energy management, and fosters social inclusion. Additionally, engaging with non-European practices from West Asia and Africa, where renewable energy has been effectively implemented in refugee camps, could offer valuable insights. For residents of occupied houses, fostering connections with other squatted housing projects, energy communities, and solidarity groups at local and international levels could facilitate knowledge exchange and provide material support for adopting sustainable energy solutions.

Christiana

Commoning

8.2. Prototype 2. Christiania (Copenhagen, DK - MAU)

Short Description (who initiated, aims and focus, type of prototype)

Christiana is an autonomous neighbourhood in central Copenhagen, Denmark, established in 1971. It was formed by squatters, activists, artists, and free-thinkers who sought to create a space that was self-governed, sustainable, and independent of traditional societal norms. Until nowadays, Christiania remains a community with its own set of rules, independent of Danish government policies, widely known for its alternative social structures.

Housing in Christiania is collectively owned by the Christiania Foundation, with no private ownership. Occupants pay a base fee of around 200 EUR/month to fund community needs like childcare, utilities, and maintenance. Financial assistance is available for those in need, while residents are expected to maintain and renovate their (often self-built) homes. Housing cannot be sold, sublet, inherited, or profited from, with low rents balanced by residents' manual and emotional labour.

Christiana is not connected to Copenhagen's district heating network and has maintained its energy independence. Until 2001, heating relied on unsustainable individual wood, coal, or oil stoves, causing air pollution and exposing households to unhealthy living conditions. The Nabovarme („neighbour heating“) project, initiated in 2001, marked a significant shift

toward systematic energy renewal. It introduced district heating systems connecting over half of Christiania's dwellings, primarily in central areas, using wood pellets. Nabovarme transformed heating from a private necessity into a collective experiment, incorporating OpenSource technology and empowering residents to take ownership of energy infrastructure and consumption. This builds on Christiania's long tradition of self-managed housing alongside other urban infrastructures. Recently, the municipality of Copenhagen has contributed 4 million DK (€536,000) to kick-start renovations, with individual households also taking initiative. At the same time, Christiania and the city have developed a Partnership Energy Analysis, resulting in an integrated energy masterplan. This plan proposes diverse heating solutions for different areas, connected through a Thermonet –a thermal pipe network covering much of Christiania– and heat pumps. Existing district heating systems will be integrated, and no new fossil-based heating systems will be introduced.

It is a community driven prototype based on collective ownership of assets and land, placing emphasis on collective

Summary table	Prototype of change
Name	Christiana
Location	Copenhagen
Type of Prototype	Community driven and Commoning
Focus	Collective management and governance structures
Beneficiaries	Residents of Christiania, especially vulnerable ones
Key Innovation	Technological and social innovation
Key outcomes	Affordable, sustainable and energy efficient housing

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strategies for advancing housing energy upgrade and innovation.

How does it address the Housing Energy Nexus (Green Energy, poverty, household type, tenancy)

Christiania's approach to the green energy transition highlights the potential for alternative pathways, characterized by do-it-yourself (DIY) practices, collective planning, user-built and owned infrastructure, independence from mainstream heating systems, and not-for-profit energy provision. Its importance rather lies in the underlying approach to housing and energy renovations. Christiania establishes a non-com-

modified model of housing provision, ensuring affordability in a region grappling with significant housing affordability pressures. In terms of energy transition, the Energy Partnership Analysis involves co-financing renovations with an emphasis on renewable energy sources. This includes utilizing of roofs for solar energy, geothermal energy for central Christiania (predominantly apartments and communal buildings), and heat storage in the nearby lake for the outer areas (primarily detached homes). These new heating systems, integrated with the existing five district heating systems, will be connected via a Thermonet –a network of thermal pipes covering much of Christiania– and heat pumps. Importantly, no new fossil-based heating solutions will be introduced.

These innovations position Christiania as a prototype for experimental, community-driven transitions that challenge conventional models of housing provision and urban sustainability.

Outcomes (Social, energetic, political)

The primary challenge, particularly for implementing the Thermonet plans, is securing adequate financing. Christiania's inability to obtain loans without state guarantees leaves

the community reliant on state authorities, who can leverage this dependency to exert influence, such as mandating the construction of social housing units on Christiania's 37 hectares of land. Additionally, the DIY energy provision model relies heavily on the voluntary efforts and dedication of local experts, making its sustainability contingent on continued community engagement and expertise.

Nonetheless, if the plans for an integrated heating system go ahead, Christiania's housing would become significantly more sustainable. However, the impact on rent and utility costs remains uncertain, although Christiania has consistently maintained housing costs well below those of the surrounding areas while keeping rent increases at reasonable levels over time.

Upscaling (replication, expansion, institutional effects)

Ultimately, the scalability of Christiania's model lies not in

Fieldwork conducted to-date: Christiania (Copenhagen, DK - MAU)

For the fieldwork in Christiania, we conducted eight in-depth qualitative interviews with various stakeholders, including residents (2), local policymakers (1), consultants (3), and researchers (2). Focus group discussions were also arranged with two academic expert groups, consisting of three participants on May 27, 2024, and five participants on June 24, 2024. Additionally, the fieldwork involved extensive non-participant observation, including field notes and approximately 50 in situ photos. We also participated in a neighbourhood meeting on the energy transition in Christiania and conducted three walk-alongs with residents.

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the specific infrastructure it has built or may build, but in its approach, which embodies a prefigurative energy transition. Christiania demonstrates that it is possible to construct OpenSource, DIY district heating systems using second-hand materials, while providing housing and utilities outside of traditional market mechanisms. This makes it a compelling example of prefigurative politics in addressing the housing-energy nexus. Furthermore, it illustrates that the provision of housing and heating under specific governance conditions –such as direct democracy through consensus– is both achievable and sustainable.

Ioannina

Commoning

8.3. Prototype 3. CommonEN (Ioannina, GR - IMPERIAL)

Short Description (who initiated, aims and focus, type of prototype)

The energy cooperative CommonEn was established in 2021 in Ioannina, Greece, in the region of Epirus. In 2023, it launched its first project, a solar park that meets the electricity needs of 35 families and local SMEs. The founding of the cooperative was supported by Electra Energy, an organisation based in Athens and Ioannina, which aims to facilitate the transition to a democratic, efficient, and sustainable energy system with citizens and local communities at its core. The main goal was to meet the electricity needs of the individuals who formed the cooperative. Concurrently, the community sought to address the electricity needs of households experiencing energy poverty. The region faces common structural challenges typical of the Greek periphery, including a high percentage of unemployment, an ageing population, declining numbers, and a low proportion of economically active inhabitants; it represents a grass-roots social innovation.

How does it address the Housing Energy Nexus (Green Energy, poverty, household type, tenancy)

While solar panels may be a technological innovation, they are notably a form of social innovation, particularly grass-roots innovation. Proponents aim to present their project as a means to reconsider energy as a common resource, thus showing a keen interest in the political, social, and educational aspects of technological use. CommonEn has estab-

lished two photovoltaic stations: one in Koutselio, located on the ground with 99.83 kW capacity, and another in Bafra, which is situated on a building with 99.9 kW capacity. These projects are distinguished by collective self-consumption through virtual energy net metering. CommonEn exemplifies grassroots social innovation by addressing local energy needs with a community-driven, non-commercial approach. The cooperative operates solar parks to supply electricity to its members without focusing on profit or large-scale production. It champions the concept of energy as a fundamental necessity rather than merely a commodity. By emphasising local collaboration and sustainability, it fosters awareness of the origins and impacts of energy production and encourages environmentally conscious practices. Although participating in the project necessitates an upfront investment, it also accommodates families who cannot afford this, enabling them to partake in the initiative.

Outcomes (Social, energetic, political)

CommonEn addresses local energy needs through a community-driven, non-commercial approach. The cooperative

Summary table	Prototype of change
Name	CommonEN
Location	Ioannina, Greece
Type of Prototype	Community and Commoning
Focus	Energy poverty and housing quality
Beneficiaries	Housing owners and low income families
Key Innovation	Social innovation, commoning & energy independence
Key outcomes	Social inclusion, low energy cost, improved quality of housing

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has solar park projects to meet the electricity requirements of its members without prioritising profit or large-scale production. It also seeks to tackle housing and energy issues for the most vulnerable social groups and is committed to including these households in a spirit project without requiring them to pay the initial fee. They have also attempted to implement energy reduction programmes by developing a project that enables community members to plan their energy-consuming activities in relation to other members and their own schedules. Additionally, they aim to implement educational and artistic projects that address the energy crisis more holistically. A small percentage of the produced energy is pro-

vided free of charge to financially disadvantaged families, offering them some relief from energy costs and the overall cost of living, thus creating an opportunity for long-term stable access to affordable energy. However, the impact is more indirect for renters in socially-owned private housing. Renters do not own the energy infrastructure and may encounter barriers to fully participating in the cooperative, as landlords typically control energy supply arrangements.

Upscaling (replication, expansion, institutional effects)

CommonEn, as part of a growing alternative ecosystem, has taken shape in the region over the past decade. In 2021, it joined forces with 19 other energy communities in Greece to form the Energy Community Coalition, a national network that promotes a cleaner, more democratic, and socially just energy system. Significant efforts are being made to access potential funding opportunities, making scaling more feasible. One important challenge remains financial limitations,

as many grassroots initiatives face resource constraints that may impede their ability to expand rapidly. Additionally, navigating the bureaucratic landscape at both the local and national levels could be challenging, especially when dealing with energy regulations and policy frameworks that may not yet fully support committee-based, decentralised energy scaling.

The prototype within the region specifically also involves balancing its growth with affordability and ensuring that the cooperative remains accessible to low-income and marginalised communities. Successful replication is contingent on local factors such as the availability of renewable resources, the level of community engagement, and the presence of

Fieldwork conducted to-date: CommonEN (Ioannina, GR - IMPERIAL)

For the fieldwork conducted in Greece, 23 in-depth qualitative expert interviews were conducted since December 2024. These interviews were strategically designed to capture diverse perspectives and involved four key stakeholder groups: academics (4), local, regional, and national policymakers (8), representatives from the energy community CommonEn (5), and representatives from similar initiatives within the local ecosystem (6). These initiatives included groups such as Tzoumakers, Pokari Project, and Habibi Works, among others. This approach enabled us to gather nuanced insights into the housing-energy nexus, community-led energy initiatives, and related policy intersections. In addition, we conducted a comprehensive cross-scale document analysis of policies relevant to the housing-energy nexus. Participatory observation also formed a crucial part of the research. We actively took part in open events, community meetings, and public discussions on energy and housing issues in Ioannina and Athens, providing an opportunity to engage deeply with the ongoing debate on the energy and housing crisis in Greece.

supportive policies at the regional and national levels. The Coalition operates in alignment with Steffen's international cooperative principles, providing a structured framework for cooperation. As such, it facilitates the exchange of best practices, educational opportunities, and resources for energy communities across Greece and beyond. One of the key obstacles is the divergence in national energy policies, regulatory frameworks, and market structures across different countries. The potential for CommonEn to become institutionalised at the local, regional, national, and European levels aligns with critical policy objectives surrounding energy access and social justice. Its integration into the Energy Community Coalition provides a strong framework for advocating systemic changes in cooperative models within formal energy and housing policies. A major barrier is ensuring accessibility for underserved communities. Addressing this issue is critical for scaling and institutionalisation, as inclusivity is central to both grassroots innovation and policy frameworks. Mainstreaming its approach in energy and housing policies requires overcoming bureaucratic inertia and the dominance of profit-driven energy providers.

8.4. Prototype 4 - WG Ketelhuis (Amsterdam, NL - UVA)

Short Description (who initiated, aims and focus, type of prototype)

Research focuses on WG-Ketelhuis, which is a community-driven energy project located in a central district of Amsterdam, initiated and operated by local residents. The project aims to establish a neighbourhood-scale heat district that offers a sustainable, affordable, and reliable alternative to the current gas-based heating system. Central to the initiative is the innovative use of heat sourced from the nearby canal, which is collectively managed and distributed as a commons-based energy solution. In detail, heat is captured during warm periods, stored in an underground system, and distributed via a warm pump to guarantee year-round heating and hot water.

The WG-Ketelhuis project began in 2018, initiated by a resident inspired to prove the feasibility of energy cooperatives. Joined by nine neighbours with expertise in fields such as engineering and social policy, they formed a core group to lead the initiative. Together, they aimed to develop a collective strategy to transition their neighbourhood away from fossil fuel reliance. The newly developed energy cooperative prioritizes common ownership and democratic decision-making, empowering residents to actively participate in the governance and operation of their heating infrastructure. By combining sustainable energy practices with a cooperative model, WG-Ketelhuis exemplifies how localized, community-

led initiatives can contribute to energy transitions and foster social cohesion.

WG-Ketelhuis can be considered as a prototype of social and frugal innovation. On the one hand, the core of the initiative lies in rethinking traditional energy systems by placing community ownership and democratic decision-making at the heart of the process. This fosters social cohesion and empowers residents to collectively manage their energy needs, addressing social inequities in access to reliable and affordable energy. It exemplifies an innovative organizational structure, rooted in the Do-It-With-Others (DIWO) approach, which emphasizes collective action, shared governance, and self-management, based on non-hierarchical decision-making and self-management of resources. Its approach offers a cost-effective and efficient alternative that directly addresses the high prices and unreliability of existing municipal services. On the other hand, by leveraging available resources, such as residual heat from nearby canals and community-based energy governance, the project delivers a sustainable and affordable energy solution that is practical and resource-efficient.

Summary table	Prototype of change
Name	WG-Ketelhuis
Location	Amsterdam
Type of Prototype	Energy community within the framework of cooperative housing
Focus	Community housing
Beneficiaries	Tenants of the cooperative and homeowners
Key Innovation	Social and frugal innovation
Key outcomes	Just housing, energy and sustainable transition

How does it address the Housing Energy Nexus (Green Energy, poverty, household type, tenancy)

WG-Ketelhuis is situated in Wilhelmina Gasthuis (WG), a former hospital area now transformed into a residential neighbourhood with artistic land uses. The area comprises 29 buildings, housing approximately 1,500 residents. Social housing corporations own 80% of the properties ensures that rents remain affordable even after renovation, with the rest owner-occupied. Within this framework, the WG-Ketelhuis cohousing group facilitates access to affordable housing outside the formal social housing system. Rents are collectivized, and the principles of affordability and community are

prioritized. In exchange for lower rents, cohousing members take on responsibilities for self-maintaining their housing units, reflecting the Do-It-Yourself (DIY) ethos. This is now being extended to self-organize alternative energy supplies. Furthermore, WG-Ketelhuis engages in collaborative efforts

to improve public spaces and mitigate the environmental impact of construction.

WG-Ketelhuis' model is distinctive in its common ownership and democratic governance, addressing issues of affordability and public participation in the district's energy transition. By empowering residents and prioritizing social equity, the initiative demonstrates how community-led innovation can drive sustainable energy solutions, offering a novel approach on the way energy systems can be collaboratively designed

and managed, promoting sustainable, inclusive, and locally adapted solutions.

Outcomes (Social, energetic, political)

WG-Ketelhuis represents a compelling case that balances the freedom of grassroots experimentation with the structure and recognition afforded by institutionalization. The initiative grants residents ownership over energy production, fostering self-determination. This grassroots control extends beyond

Fieldwork conducted to-date: WG Kettelhuis (Amsterdam, NL - UVA)

For the fieldwork in the Netherlands, we carried out 20 in-depth qualitative expert interviews, attended two group meetings, one walk-in housing consultation session, and organized a technical workshop session. The interviews were conducted with members of academia (2), local policymakers (1), local energy networks (2), housing counsellors (2), activists (3), market actors (1), social housing employees (1), and housing energy community members (13)*. The in-depth interviews with housing energy community members typically lasted around 1.5 hours and combined structured interview questions with narrative-based techniques, focusing on the experiences of the interviewees. Additionally, we conducted two walk-along interviews with two resident activists and one local policymaker. These walks through neighbourhoods in transition explored the physical aspects of change, highlighting housing neglect, ongoing renovations, and the subterranean infrastructure related to the heat transition.

In addition, we engaged in extensive observation and deep listening and attended two group meetings organized by the housing energy cooperative Ketelhuis WG. These meetings involved 5–8 core group members discussing their progress and challenges. We attended a walk-in housing consultation session, where area residents sought advice from the collective and the social housing employee about the upcoming project. These observations were recorded in field notes. A technical skill-sharing session bringing together participants from this prototype and another one also in Amsterdam (Thermo Bello) is also planned.

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self-sufficiency, as the cooperative's democratic organization embodies energy democracy. Each member can vote on decisions, participate directly, and voice opinions, ensuring a more inclusive and equitable decision-making process compared to large-scale energy providers. Most residents continue to benefit from low rents, even among those earning significantly above the social minimum. Transitioning to an independent energy system promises lower energy costs compared to other sustainable options, greater energy stability, and protection from market fluctuations.

Upscaling (replication, expansion, institutional effects)

WG-Ketelhuis demonstrates a localized approach to decentralized energy solutions that, while impactful, cannot be up-scaled beyond its spatial boundaries. The initiative operates in highly context-specific ways, making replication feasible only to a limited extent –for instance in places with proximity to water resources– and through practices that adapt to local conditions. While its current model focuses on renewable energy sources, it offers opportunities for expansion, such as incorporating additional renewable energy technologies or integrating other energy communities through cooperative electricity systems. Moreover, WG-Ketelhuis serves as a learning community and knowledge hub in Amsterdam, offering a prototype for decentralized and local energy alternatives. Its activities, such as developing workbooks, hosting workshops, and fostering learning communities, empower others to adopt similar principles in own contexts. These principles –small-scale, decentralized, and community-driven– are transferable, yet Ketelhuis WG cannot function as a universal blueprint due to its deep local embeddedness. Instead, it provides inspiration and practical insights, allowing other communities and municipalities to tailor their own energy initiatives to their unique needs and circumstances.

Barcelona

Community

8.5. Prototype 5. Barcelona digital Platform for sharing information on Housing Conditions- Reviu (Barcelona, ESP, IDRA)

Short Description (who initiated, aims and focus, type of prototype)

Reviu is an online platform that allows tenants to openly share reviews about their experiences with privately rented apartments and landlords. Users can evaluate various aspects, including the condition of the apartment, thermal comfort, the balance between housing quality and rent, as well as the communication and relationship with the landlord or real-estate company.

The prototype was initiated in 2024 in Barcelona by IDRA, the Institute of Urban Research, which is a cooperative think tank dedicated to promoting social and ecological justice through research and education. Concerned about the growing housing affordability crisis in a region with a rising tenant population, and deeply involved in addressing housing inequalities and advocating for the right to housing, IDRA set out to develop an online tool designed to enable a balanced and transparent exchange of information within the private rental housing market. It should be noted that so far in Spain, there are two real-estate market platforms that offer information on the availability of properties and the requested monthly rents, and in Barcelona there is also relevant platform managed by the municipality. In this context, Reviu stands out as a platform that offers the missing information from the tenant side of view, whose perspectives and experiences are not included as data in existing real estate information platforms.

Within this framework, Reviu could be considered as both a technological innovation and a communing practice. As a digital tool it generates information from tenant experiences supplementing existing information from real-estate platforms. Simultaneously, it facilitates tenants to collaboratively contribute reviews and share information about housing conditions, energy efficiency, and landlord practices generating a community of tenant reviewers.

How does it address the Housing Energy Nexus (Green Energy, poverty, household type, tenancy)

The aim of Reviu is to address the asymmetry in real-estate data exchange that often favours speculative behaviours from landlords and incentivise practices that sustain rents in affordable levels. At the same time, online reviews regarding the properties' energy efficiency and thermal comfort helps to the construction of information on the energy consumption requirements of each asset, aligning Reviu with broader efforts to promote sustainable housing.

Despite the growing professionalization of real estate mar-

Summary table	Prototype of change
Name	Reviu
Location	Barcelona
Type of Prototype	Community Digital Platform
Focus	Tenants (in privately rented housing), affordable housing and energy efficiency
Beneficiaries	City of Barcelona
Key Innovation	Technological innovation & Community involvement
Key outcomes	Symmetry and transparency in information of the housing condition in the residential real-estate market.

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ket operations, tenants with rental contracts frequently face discriminatory and speculative practices that contribute to displacement, exclusion from housing access, and inflated rent increases. These issues disproportionately impact vulnerable social groups, particularly migrants and female-headed households, who are more likely to experience multiple forms of housing injustice, including neglect in property maintenance, evictions, and displacement pressures. In response to these systemic challenges, Reviu actively combats real estate discrimination by offering a platform that amplifies tenants' voices and holds landlords accountable for exclusionary practices in the housing market.

Outcomes (Social, energetic, political)

Reviu seeks to contribute to a more affordable and accessible housing system by increasing transparency and accountability in the rental market. By publicly disclosing actual rental prices and aligning them with housing costs, Reviu has the potential to drive market practices toward what can be considered „just“ and fair pricing within the housing mar-

ket framework. This transparency in information pressures landlords and real estate agencies to deter speculative pricing and adhere to equitable pricing standards. Additionally, Reviu provides crucial data on the thermal insulation and living conditions of rental properties, particularly regarding temperature regulation. This is designed to motivate landlords to improve the energy efficiency and overall comfort of their properties to secure better reviews, thereby increasing demand for well-maintained units. In doing so, Reviu has to

potential to incentivize landlords and real estate agencies to invest in energy upgrades, especially where affordable energy solutions are most needed. Due to the platform's relatively recent launch, it is not yet possible to measure its impact in the privately rented housing market and across different social groups.

Upscaling (replication, expansion, institutional effects)

The upscaling potential of Reviu relies on the fact operates as an open-source platform, allowing it to be replicated and adapted in other regions without reliance on a specific pro-

Fieldwork conducted to-date: Barcelona digital Platform for sharing information on Housing Conditions - Reviu (Barcelona, ESP, IDRA)

For the fieldwork in Barcelona (Reviu prototype), we conducted 15 in-depth qualitative expert interviews and two focus group discussions. The interviews were carried out with members of academia (2), local policymakers (2), real estate market investors (3), activists (4), citizen participation NGOs (1), architects and planners (2), and technology experts (1). The focus group discussions were organized with some of the prototype's creators and Board Members with each group comprising four members, including activists (all of whom self-identified as such), project coordinators, a housing expert, an initial project developer, and a current housing researcher.

Additionally, during the fieldwork, we engaged extensively in non-participant observation, documenting field notes and in situ photos. These observations were conducted during sessions with project coordinators, encounters with local government representatives (where the prototype was presented), advisory board meetings, presentations to members of the Chamber of Real Estate Agents, and meetings with the volunteer team handling programming tasks for Reviu. Furthermore, we analyzed a "live" diary maintained by the prototype's creators to record milestones, conducting periodic follow-up sessions with them to track their progress.

programming team. Within the geographical context of Spain, the prototype can be easily replicated from the robust network of citizen organizations capable of serving as both the driving force and advocates for the platform's expansion and impact. Additionally, a potential collaboration with the municipality of Barcelona (decision pending at the moment of writing) could offer a significant boost in the upscaling of the effort.

However, developing and maintaining a user-friendly digital platform requires substantial investment, particularly in hiring skilled technology and programming professionals. Companies operating in the tech sector typically need a high and steady cash flow to support ongoing development, updates, and technical support. However, this level of financial stability is not yet characteristic of the Reviu prototype, limiting its capacity for large-scale expansion and sustained technological improvement. Second, generating consistent user engagement through reviews poses a considerable challenge, as participation is often polarized, with users typically motivated to leave feedback only after extremely positive or negative experiences. This results in a limited and potentially skewed data set, undermining the platform's goal of providing actual information on rental properties. The difficulty in converting passive followers into active contributors hampers the platform's ability to scale up and foster transparency in the rental market. Addressing these financial and engagement challenges is crucial for Reviu's successful upscaling from the Barcelona to the Spanish and EU context and beyond.

Copenhagen

Community

8.6. Prototype 6. Non-profit Housing Associations (Denmark, DK - MAU)

Short Description (who initiated, aims and focus, type of prototype)

Non-profit housing associations (NPHAs) in Denmark represent a prototype for affordable and democratically governed housing. While not state-owned, NPHAs receive state subsidies and are integral to the government's broader mission to provide affordable housing for all. The sector operates under the umbrella of the Danish Federation for Non-Profit Associations (BL), established in 1919 to address the shortage of affordable housing. Today, NPHAs cater to both the general population and specific vulnerable groups like students, the elderly, and the disabled, housing approximately 20% of the Danish population. Rents are determined based on operating, maintenance, and capital costs, ensuring accessibility and affordability. Municipalities play a supervisory role, overseeing the sector, disposing of every fourth letting, and evaluating new developments. Governance is decentralized, with tenant-elected boards managing individual estates and making decisions through annual meetings. This model exemplifies a balanced approach to affordable housing provision, combining public support, community participation, and cost transparency.

The umbrella organization of Denmark's non-profit housing associations (NPHAs), BL, has demonstrated a commitment to fostering energy communities, particularly in Copenhagen, where dense urban development limits the feasibility of renewable energy options like wind power. A notable

example is Øbro95, a non-profit housing association where residents have established solar panels linked to a lithium battery for energy storage. Plans to expand this system with a second battery remain contingent on financing, highlighting the financial challenges of scaling autonomous energy production. This energy community emerged after significant negotiation between the housing association and Copenhagen municipality, eventually benefiting from a partnership with green software developer Enyday, whose digital platform introduced variable spot-price electricity billing. This system encourages environmentally friendly behaviour, optimizes cost distribution based on consumption patterns, and reduces administrative workloads. However, Øbro95 is located in a well-off, gentrified area, raising critical questions about the scalability of such energy transitions in less affluent non-profit estates that may face additional barriers, such as stigmatization, demolition, or privatization.

How does it address the Housing Energy Nexus (Green Energy, poverty, household type, tenancy)

Recent policy developments in Denmark have aimed at cur-

Summary table	Prototype of change
Name	Non-profit Housing Associations (NB)/ Øbro95
Location	Copenhagen
Type of Prototype	Community - Democratic decision making for the housing energy nexus
Focus	Housing affordability and energy community
Beneficiaries	Tenants of non-profit associations
Key Innovation	Social innovation and technology engagement
Key outcomes	Housing affordability and sustainability

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bing the scope of non-profit housing associations (NPHAs). First, a mid-2000s attempt to commodify social housing by allowing tenants to purchase their units; second, the 2018 „Ghetto Law“ targeted areas classified as „hard ghettos“ based on demographic statistics, mandating a reduction of social housing to 40%, with the remainder privatized, converted, or demolished; and third, flexible letting regulations shifted tenant selection priorities from waiting times to favouring specific groups, such as students and employed individuals, ostensibly to promote social mix. These measures reflect a trend toward commodification and a redefinition of social housing’s role in Danish society.

Against this backdrop, Øbro95 exemplifies how the housing-energy nexus can be addressed through democratic decision-making and affordability mechanisms in the rental sector. The estate demonstrates that green transitions can be achieved without reliance on landlord decisions or the risk of substantial rent increases, as decision-making power rests with the tenants. This underscores the critical role of democratic governance structures in ensuring fair and inclusive transitions to sustainability. Additionally, Øbro95 provides direct economic benefits to residents through reduced energy bills and an informal subsidy system. Excess energy generated is sold back to the grid, and the revenues are distributed among households, further enhancing affordability. Given that many peripheral non-profit cooperative housing associations –often housing low-income groups and individuals with non-European backgrounds– share similar democratic decision-making structures, Øbro95 highlights the potential for housing and energy renovations to be implemented broadly across the sector without imposing significant financial burdens on tenants.

Outcomes (Social, energetic, political)

The Øbro95’s initiative represents a potential model for a just transition in the housing-energy nexus, demonstrating how affordability and sustainability can be achieved simultaneously. In the case of Øbro95 this may be sustained via

the availability of housing below market prices, that ensure greater affordability and tenure security compared to the private rental sector, and via energy renovations that reduce greenhouse gas emissions without causing rent increases, while benefiting tenants through the redistribution of revenue from selling excess energy back to the grid. However, broader challenges persist, such as the 2018 compulsory „flexible letting,“ which prioritizes students and employed applicants, potentially restricting access to affordable housing

for vulnerable groups within the framework of the weakening influence of BL, which has limited the ability to advocate for critical legislative changes, such as enabling energy-sharing between buildings within associations.

Upscaling (replication, expansion, institutional effects)

The scaling-up of the Øbro95 energy initiative presents both significant opportunities and challenges. When Øbro95 was approved, the mayor of Copenhagen pledged to use it as a model for the city’s energy transition. However, subsequent regulations have introduced substantial barriers, limiting the establishment of energy communities in social housing areas and hindering compliance with EU directives on energy transition. A major obstacle is the Danish legislation of May 2023, which prohibits electricity sharing between non-contiguous buildings, rendering the Øbro95 system legally infeasible for many other social housing estates, parti-

Fieldwork conducted to-date: Non-profit Housing Associations (Denmark, DK - MAU)

For the fieldwork on the non-profit social housing sector, we conducted eight in-depth qualitative interviews. These interviews included residents (2), senior managers in the non-profit sector (1), representatives from financing agencies (1), and researchers (4).

Focus group discussions were held with two academic expert groups, one consisting of three participants, and another with five participants.

Additionally, during the fieldwork, we engaged in non-participant observation through a walk-along with residents, which resulted in detailed fieldwork notes and in situ photos (approximately 20).

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cularly in lower-density areas. Øbro95's success was also contingent on substantial social capital: one of the project's initiators, a resident and energy journalist, leveraged strong connections to local government, and the socially and economically well-positioned residents played a crucial role in the project's implementation.

Despite these challenges, the broader European social and cooperative housing sector offers unique potential for replicating Øbro95's energy community model. Legal and regulatory restrictions across Europe frequently reinforce existing power dynamics in the energy market, favouring large, traditional players over local and non-profit initiatives. While the EU's REPowerEU plan estimates that rooftop solar power could meet 25% of the EU's electricity consumption, national policies often impede such efforts. Addressing these legal and social barriers is essential to unlocking the transformative potential of energy communities within the housing-energy nexus.

Barcelona

Social entrepreneurship

8.7. Prototype 7 - WikiHousing (Barcelona, ESP - IDRA)

Short Description (who initiated, aims and focus, type of prototype)

WikiHousing is a participatory initiative of social innovation in Barcelona that aims at producing affordable, environmentally friendly and sustainable public housing solutions attuned to the needs of inner-city population.

The prototype was initiated by two inspired architects, David Baro and David Juarez, aiming to deliver cost-effective, sustainable, and collaboratively produced public housing that addresses housing affordability pressures, but also challenges dominant narratives about the lack of resources, and space for public housing in Barcelona's inner city. By presenting WikiHousing as a project proposal to city's BIT Habitat Foundation, they were granted a municipally-owned plot of land for the project's development after winning the competition.

Based on light weight balloon frame construction and co-design processes that rely on public participation throughout the construction phase, Wikihousing promotes a "Do it with others" approach to urban design. This model empowers participants to actively partake in the development of their own homes while fostering community self-management, envisioning a housing model of public community.

The prototype combines technological innovation –through sustainable construction material and methods and modular design– with participatory governance, engaging future resi-

dents in the decision-making and collective management of the building process.

How does it address the Housing Energy Nexus (Green Energy, poverty, household type, tenancy)

WikiHousing utilizes wood as a primary construction material in combination with prefabricated components to create lightweight, sustainable structures. Wood not only offers natural durability and thermal insulation but also significantly reduces water and energy consumption typically associated with the transportation, manufacturing, and installation of conventional building materials. By prioritizing sustainable resources and integrating passive design strategies –such as natural ventilation, optimal solar orientation, and thermal mass– WikiHousing fosters the development of highly energy-efficient housing solutions.

WikiHousing emerges as a pioneering prototype that effectively addresses the critical intersection between housing accessibility and energy sustainability. By considering the

Summary table	Prototype of change
Name	Wikihousing
Location	Barcelona
Type of Prototype	Social Entrepreneurship - Construction of sustainable and affordable housing
Focus	Public housing, tenants in housing vulnerability
Beneficiaries	Inner city, gendered and vulnerable population/ Local state
Key Innovation	Technological innovation & Collective Management Governance
Key outcomes	Transferable blueprint for energy efficient, cost-effective and participative public housing solutions.

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housing needs of public housing tenants –particularly undocumented migrants, women, and young people– the prototype evolves into a powerful tool for social inclusion. It not only provides safe and affordable housing but also offers opportunities for hands-on training in construction, empowering marginalized groups with valuable skills and fostering economic self-sufficiency. Furthermore, by actively involving residents in the co-design and building process, the project promotes their integration into the social and cultural fabric of the city, strengthening their participation in the shared commons of urban life.

At its full potential, the prototype aims to advance publicly

protected housing offered at below-market prices, ensuring collective participation, affordability, high-quality and energy-efficient housing standards.

Outcomes (Social, energetic, political)

The prototype fosters a critical understanding of the urgent need for sustainable, energy-efficient, affordable, and co-designed housing. It also tackles existing social and labour inequalities by actively involving citizens in hands-on training in construction and architectural design, equipping them with new skills and professional qualifications. It responds

to the urgent demand for affordable public housing in a city strained by successive waves of gentrification, touristification, and housing financialization – reducing the typical public housing delivery timeline from seven years to just seven months. Finally, the combined reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and the prevention of potential rent increases– ensured through tenant participation and self-management of housing affairs– offers a promising solution to the housing-energy vulnerability nexus. This approach positions the

prototype as a model for resisting green and other forms of low-carbon gentrification.

Upscaling (replication, expansion, institutional effects)

Central to this model is its open-source architectural and construction approach, designed to be a replicable framework for delivering cost-effective and sustainable housing solutions. The prototype’s significantly lower construction costs, reduced energy and water consumption, and accelerated building timeline –especially when compared to conventional methods– make it particularly suited for addressing urgent public housing needs. This relevance is further amplified by recent policy developments, notably the establishment of the first European Housing Commissioner, which is expected to enhance European Union support and funding

Fieldwork conducted to-date: Christiania (Copenhagen, DK - MAU)

For the fieldwork in Barcelona related to the Wikihousing prototype, we conducted 15 in-depth qualitative expert interviews and two focus group discussions.

The interviews were conducted with local policymakers (3), architects and planners (3), construction workers and volunteers (4), an environmental engineer (1), NGO and housing advocates (2), and real estate agents (2).

Focus group discussions were arranged with various actors involved in the prototype. Each focus group included four members with the following profiles: architects, project managers, construction workers and volunteers, and engineers.

Additionally, during the fieldwork, we engaged in non-participant observation, which involved taking detailed fieldwork notes, documenting meetings between prototype leaders, lawyers, and administration representatives, and capturing in situ photos.

for innovative housing initiatives. This evolving policy landscape creates favourable conditions for scaling projects like WikiHousing across EU member states, positioning it as a viable solution to the growing demand for affordable and sustainable urban housing.

However, critical barriers persist, notably inconsistent funding streams, bureaucratic complexities in public financing, and rigid national tender laws that hinder the integration of design and construction processes. The model's reliance on tailor-made, non-standardized solutions complicates industrial scalability, while regulatory diversity across EU regions and the challenge of building trust with public stakeholders may further obstruct widespread adoption.

Brixton

Social entrepreneurship

8.8. Prototype 8. Brixton Energy (London, UK - IMPERIAL)

Short Description (who initiated, aims and focus, type of prototype)

Brixton Energy (BE) is a not-for-profit citizen cooperative based in South London that seeks to promote the generation of clean, renewable energy while ensuring that these energy solutions are accessible and directly benefit the local community. It accomplishes this through active community engagement, a community shareholder system, creating green jobs (through projects and training), and reinvesting revenues into community energy initiatives. Operating under a community-owned cooperative model (where members are shareholders), it directs profits into a Community Energy Efficiency Fund (CEEF) and is both organizationally and financially embedded within the community. It also maintains strong ties with the local borough, which provides financial and institutional support.

How does it address the Housing Energy Nexus (Green Energy, poverty, household type, tenancy)

BE combines low-cost energy with a community investment fund that aims at improving the energy performance of the housing stock of often low quality social housing. It is particularly focused on vulnerable households. Yet because of the investment model with members investing or buying into the project, it also excludes a large part of those households. By funnelling (20%) of the profits into the CEEF, it is able to also help these groups with cost reduction measures. In addition,

through its training programmes it aims to help people get a job in the green energy sector. By using a community model it aims to improve social cohesion, empower local residents and support a sense of place and community.

Outcomes (Social, energetic, political)

BE has implemented three PV projects so far, totalling 135 kW and resulting in a reduction of approximately 50 tonnes of CO₂ thus far. By promoting community-owned projects, many participants have been empowered as they are actively involved in the decision-making process and the distribution of benefits. By offering electricity at a lower rate, it has also contributed to tackling energy poverty, although BE still finds it challenging to reach and engage these individuals since the ownership model requires an upfront investment as well. The CEEF supports various local initiatives that promote energy savings by subsidising equipment and providing education. BE's initiatives have also fostered skill development and empowerment by offering training and workshops that enable residents to acquire skills in renewable energy technology. For instance, this includes solar

Summary table	Prototype of change
Name	Brixton Energy
Location	London, UK
Type of Prototype	Community Driven and Commoning
Focus	Energy poverty and housing quality
Beneficiaries	Housing owners and low-income families
Key Innovation	Energy price reduction, green job training, community fund
Key outcomes	Social inclusion, low energy cost, traing programmes, educational outreach

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panel installation and energy auditing. Furthermore, through the involvement of locals, it strengthens social cohesion and nurtures a sense of pride among the residents.

Upscaling (replication, expansion, institutional effects)

BE has been very influential within the London context and has been replicated in other boroughs such as Hackney and Lambeth. At the regional and national levels, it has inspired a multitude of initiatives, and local councils and organisations increasingly view BE as a model for bringing affordable community-owned renewable energy to housing estates and underprivileged neighbourhoods. It was also the main founder

of its parent organisation, Repowering London, which promotes the institutionalisation of community ownership while delivering training programmes, internships, and educational outreach to empower local communities. At the European scale, BE participates in REScoop, a federation of renewable energy cooperatives, and through Repowering London, it is a member of the European Community Power Coalition. Its institutional impact and upscaling stem from its strong connection with Lambeth Council, and its success has influenced the London Environment Strategy. However, the inte-

gration into the broader urban planning framework remains limited. One of the key barriers to upscaling at the national and international levels has been the financial and institutional backing.

gration into the broader urban planning framework remains limited. One of the key barriers to upscaling at the national and international levels has been the financial and institutional backing.

Fieldwork conducted to-date: Brixton Energy (London, UK - IMPERIAL)

For the fieldwork conducted in England, we successfully carried out 25 in-depth qualitative expert interviews. These interviews were strategically designed to capture diverse perspectives and involved three key groups of stakeholders: academics (6), local and national policymakers (7), and representatives from various organizations (12). The organisations included groups such as Repowering London, Brixton Energy, Transition Town Brixton, and Community Energy London. This approach enabled us to gather nuanced insights into the housing-energy nexus, community-led energy initiatives, and policy intersections.

In addition to the interviews, we conducted a comprehensive cross-scale document analysis of policies relevant to the housing-energy nexus. This analysis covered local, regional, and national levels, helping to identify gaps, synergies, and challenges within current policy frameworks. Together, these methods provide a robust foundation for understanding the socio-political, economic, and environmental dimensions shaping energy justice and housing policy in England.

Burgas

Social entrepreneurship

8.9. Prototype 9. CODE HOUSING Micro-loans (Burgas, BG - CSD)

Short Description (who initiated, aims and focus, type of prototype)

Habitat Bulgaria is the national branch of “Habitat for Humanity”, a global non-profit organization dedicated to providing affordable and adequate housing for vulnerable and low-income families. In 2022, Habitat Bulgaria launched its Community Support Programme (CODE HOUSING) aimed at facilitating accessible housing improvements for vulnerable families. This initiative is supported by funding from Habitat for Humanity International’s Global Mission Fund and the Medicor Foundation. Operating across six Bulgarian cities – Burgas, Blagoevgrad, Kyustendil, Rakitovo, Sliven, and Targovishte– the programme provides microfinance solutions for essential housing upgrades, delivers life skills workshops to enhance household resilience, and finances small-scale local initiatives designed to strengthen community cohesion and support sustainable development.

Through the promotion of diverse energy efficiency solutions –ranging from basic interventions such as high-quality external insulation to more comprehensive renewable energy measures like the installation of solar panels– CODE Housing adopts a holistic approach that extends beyond financial assistance. This prototype prioritizes community engagement and empowerment, fostering active participation in the decision-making process. This is facilitated through collaboration with local NGOs, community leaders, and sub-

ject-matter experts that ensures that implemented solutions are tailored to the unique needs of each community across the six cities, thereby enhancing the program’s overall effectiveness and socio-environmental impact.

Key actors and stakeholders in the initiative are low-income homeowners, homeowners’ associations and social housing tenants, who serve as both active participants and direct beneficiaries of the program. Additionally, local authorities play a pivotal role in the coordination and management of renovation initiatives, ensuring alignment with regulatory frameworks and community needs. The involvement of professional groups, including energy consultants and construction companies, is also critical, as they contribute specialized technical expertise necessary for the effective implementation of energy-efficient and sustainable housing solutions. This multi-stakeholder collaboration enhances the program’s capacity to deliver comprehensive and impactful outcomes. Therefore, CODE HOUSING may be considered as a prototype of financial innovation and capacity building.

Summary table	Prototype of change
Name	CODE Housing Microloans
Location	Burgas, Blagoevgrad, Kyustendil, Rakitovo, Sliven, and Targovishte
Type of Prototype	Social Entrepreneurship - Interest-free microloans for housing energy upgrades
Focus	Tenants and homeowners of depleted housing stock
Beneficiaries	Vulnerable homeowners, homeowner associations and local governments
Key Innovation	Financial innovation & capacity building
Key outcomes	Energy efficient housing, living standard improvement

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How does it address the Housing Energy Nexus (Green Energy, poverty, household type, tenancy)

In Bulgaria, the primary housing challenge lies not in access to housing –given that 39% of all residential buildings are not occupied– but in access to quality housing, particularly for low-income households. While high-income families increasingly relocate to newly constructed buildings that comply with modern energy efficiency standards, economically disadvantaged families are often confined to older, energy-inefficient multi-family residential buildings. These households frequently lack the financial means to undertake even basic repairs or essential upgrades, despite the fact that relatively modest investments could significantly improve their living conditions. At the same time, access to financing remains a significant barrier, as commercial banks are generally reluctant to offer microloans to low-income families due to financial risks, whereas national financing programs provide only limited support. The financial support provided by CODE HOUSING fills in this structural gap, by facilitating households to renovate and energetically upgrade their homes.

Outcomes (Social, energetic, political)

By providing interest-free microloans, the program actively fosters financial inclusion and empowers low-income families to undertake essential improvements, with a particular

focus on addressing energy inefficiency. In detail, in the private rental housing sector, microloans play a crucial role in stabilizing housing for vulnerable tenants who may otherwise face eviction or rising living costs due to landlords' neglect of property maintenance. CODE Housing effectively addresses this issue by providing financial support for property upgrades when landlords are unwilling or unable to invest in necessary improvements. For owner-occupied housing, CODE Housing facilitates low-income homeowners to afford critical repairs and upgrades.

Moreover, the program's emphasis on green energy solutions not only mitigates fuel poverty but also lowers energy

Fieldwork conducted to-date: CODE HOUSING Microloans (Burgas, BG - CSD) and Prototype 10 – One Stop Shop (Bulgaria, BG - CSD)

To develop a detailed understanding of the socio-economic conditions in Gabrovo and Burgas, which host the two Bulgarian prototypes (9 and 10), and to assess how each prototype contributes to alleviating energy poverty and housing inefficiency, we conducted 16 in-depth qualitative expert interviews over eight months (May-December 2024). CSD representatives visited the two cities four times, documenting their work with visual material, including 10 photos.

The interviews were conducted both in person and online with 22 representatives from the following groups:

- **National authorities:** Energy and Water Regulation Commission (2) and Sustainable Energy Development Agency (2).
- **Local authorities:** Municipalities of Gabrovo (1), Burgas (2), and Sofia (1).
- **Academia:** Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (1).
- **NGOs:** Habitat for Humanity Bulgaria (2), Energy Efficiency Center EnEffect (3), and Greenpeace (2).
- **Independent clean energy power producer:** Rezolv Energy (1).
- **Legal consultant companies:** 2 companies (3 representatives).
- **Renewable energy companies (RES):** 3 companies (6 representatives).

Key discussion topics included:

- Investigating factors affecting energy citizenship, particularly barriers preventing underrepresented social groups from engaging in the energy sector.
- Alleviating energy poverty through targeted financial mechanisms for small-scale energy efficiency improvements.
- Legal recommendations to promote renewable energy investments.
- Decentralization of power generation and liberalization of Bulgaria's electricity market.

costs, enabling families to align their homes with energy efficiency standards. Complementing the financial support, the program offers additional educational workshops on home maintenance and energy management, equipping families with the practical knowledge and skills necessary to maintain and sustain long-term improvements to their living environments. These are specifically significant for marginalized communities, including the Roma population, who are disproportionately burdened by substandard housing conditions and high energy expenses.

Upscaling (replication, expansion, institutional effects)

The CODE Housing initiative in Bulgaria demonstrates considerable potential for upscaling at both local and regional levels. Expanding the program's reach could greatly enhance its impact by providing targeted financial support to a wider range of vulnerable populations typically excluded from traditional financial markets. This expansion would not only improve housing conditions but also drive greater energy savings, contributing to more sustainable and also inclusive communities.

Key enabling factors include the program's alignment with EU and national targets for the green transition and its targeted approach to addressing housing inequalities. The initiative's innovative and modular design, which integrates financial assistance, skills-building workshops, and community-led projects, offers the flexibility of adaptation to various contexts and needs. Strategic partnerships with local governments and civil society organizations could further support scalability by leveraging existing networks and resources to facilitate program implementation.

The expansion of the CODE Housing initiative faces several significant challenges that may hinder its growth and long-term impact. Financial sustainability remains a primary concern, as the program's provision of interest-free microloans demands consistent and stable funding sources. Further complications arise from regional disparities in housing markets, economic conditions, and varying levels of community engagement, all of which may limit the program's uniform applicability and effectiveness.

Gabrovo

Institutional participatory

8.10. Prototype 10. One Stop Shop (Bulgaria, BG - CSD)

Short Description (who initiated, aims and focus, type of prototype)

Research focuses on the **one-stop shop (OSS) initiatives for housing energy upgrades** in Bulgaria. Introduced as measure under the Bulgarian Recovery and Resilience Plan, these centers are designed to streamline the renovation process by reducing administrative burdens and offering expert guidance on regulatory, technical, and financial aspects of energy efficiency projects. By consolidating information, expert advice, and financial assistance under one roof, the initiative simplifies what is often a complex and resource-intensive process, ensuring that energy-efficient solutions are both achievable, accessible and sustainable.

Bulgaria established its first energy centres in Gabrovo and Burgas, offering a one-stop-shop for citizens seeking to enhance the energy efficiency of their buildings. This initiative integrates affordable housing support with green energy practices, creating opportunities for low-income families to access improved living conditions and reduce energy costs. Beyond direct support, the centre fosters community engagement by hosting workshops that empower citizens to design and implement sustainable solutions in their homes. By addressing financial and knowledge barriers, this innovative approach ensures that energy-efficient renovations are accessible to those who might otherwise lack the resources to pursue housing energy efficiency.

The customer service innovation in Bulgaria's one-stop-shop energy centers lies in their ability to serve as a single point of contact for comprehensive support, empowering citizens –particularly low-income families– to make informed decisions about accessible and cost-effective energy-efficient home improvements.

How does it address the Housing Energy Nexus (Green Energy, poverty, household type, tenancy)

Access to affordable and energy efficient housing in Bulgaria is characterized by deep inequalities intensified by energy inefficiency, rising housing costs, and substandard living conditions. Bulgarian households spend 23.3% of their disposable income on housing, ranking sixth highest in the EU, while housing prices have surged by 86.7% between 2015 and 2023, driven by increased construction costs and real estate investments. These affordability pressures are particularly severe for young people, who, on average, delay leaving their parental homes, and in rural areas where often houses remain vacant. Compounding these challenges is the energy inefficiency of the housing stock, with 22.5% of

Summary table	Prototype of change
Name	One Stop Shop
Location	Gabrovo and Burgas
Type of Prototype	Institutional Participatory. Advice and information for housing energy upgrades
Focus	Homeowners of depleted housing stock
Beneficiaries	Low income households, elderly and vulnerable social groups
Key Innovation	Customer-centric service innovation
Key outcomes	Energy efficient and affordable housing

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the population –the highest rate in the EU– unable to adequately heat their homes due to poor insulation and high energy costs. Rising construction material costs hinder the adoption of energy-efficient building practices, further marginalizing low-income groups. While Bulgaria boasts an 85% homeownership rate, this figure masks significant disparities, as many rely on inherited homes or extended family arrangements rather than accessing the, already hardly affordable, new housing market.

Through a consolidated service framework, OSS initiatives facilitate access to better housing and energy efficient conditions. OSS eliminate common barriers, such as challenges in finding reliable contractors, limited access to financing, and complex technical requirements. This approach is especially beneficial for vulnerable populations, who may lack the knowledge, the capacity or resources to undertake housing energy-efficient renovations on their own. By offering tailored advice and financial support, including access to grants or loans, OSS programs empower low-income households to enhance their living conditions, reduce energy costs, and address energy poverty.

Outcomes (Social, energetic, political)

Bulgaria faces the highest level of fuel poverty in the EU, driven by the low energy efficiency of its housing stock and reliance on polluting fuels like firewood and coal. Although EU funds finance energy efficiency and decarbonization efforts, the universal grant-based approach lacks socio-economic targeting, limiting its impact on vulnerable groups. Structural challenges, such as poor insulation and limited resources for sustainable renovation, persist despite the efforts of OSS.

OSS are particularly successful at the local level because they can align closely with local policies, economic structures, and specific community needs, tailoring solutions for maximum impact. Additionally, local-level knowledge-sharing and capacity-building programs enable communities to adopt best practices from established OSS models, ensuring more effective and sustainable implementation.

Upscaling (replication, expansion, institutional effects)

The OSS model for residential energy renovation shows significant potential for upscaling in both European and international contexts due to its holistic approach to addressing energy poverty and driving renovation efforts. Policy frameworks like the European Green Deal and the Renovation Wave Initiative provide robust support for this expansion by

encouraging Member States to adopt OSS models through financial incentives and binding energy performance targets. Europe's mature regulatory environment, including standardized energy performance certificates and renovation requirements, further enables consistent service delivery across Member States. Internationally, the customer-centric design of OSS allows for adaptation to diverse housing conditions, energy markets, and policy environments. However, key challenges include the variability of policy and regulatory frameworks across countries, which complicates local adaptation. Financial sustainability is another pressing issue, as OSS often depend on public subsidies or external funding,

which may be scarce in certain regions. Additionally, fragmented construction and energy renovation markets, particularly in less developed areas, pose barriers to creating the integrated value chain essential for OSS success.

Thessaloniki

Institutional participatory

8.11. Prototype 11. Housing Thessaloniki (Thessaloniki, GR - KIT)

Short Description (who initiated, aims and focus, type of prototype)

Housing Thessaloniki is a pilot program decided to address two crucial urban and social challenges: the housing crisis and energy poverty in Thessaloniki, Greece. The project has been initiated top down through the state in a collaboration with several governmental bodies such as the municipality of Thessaloniki, regional authorities and local organisations. It aims to provide an alternative to the traditional housing market based on homeownership and lack of social housing. This initiative focuses on renovating and energy upgrading 30 publicly owned apartments to create safe affordable and energy efficient housing for vulnerable groups.

A survey estimated the number of vacant properties to approximately 700,000 unused and non-residential properties in the city. A significant portion of these properties are small, situated in less desirable areas and disconnected from the electricity grid. By integrating part of this housing stock into a comprehensive network of affordable housing, the project aims to provide immediate relief to those in need while establishing long-term sustainable housing solutions. The beneficiaries, who are primarily low-income households, must meet certain social economic criteria, yet to be decided upon.

How does it address the Housing Energy Nexus (Green Energy, poverty, household type, tenancy)

The properties included in the program are primarily located

in central and western Thessaloniki. These areas are home to a mix of low-income residents and immigrant communities that face precarious housing conditions and high energy costs. By prioritising these areas, Housing Thessaloniki targets households most in need of stable, affordable housing scattered throughout the city. It focuses on a specific segment of society, targeting individuals whose economic and social status, as well as standard type, make them particularly vulnerable. Moreover, the programme addresses the challenges of housing affordability and energy costs while activating the city's building stock, making it available to residents under the supervision of the state rather than the free market. The project departs from traditional approaches by integrating energy upgrades into its core design, ensuring that beneficiaries not only gain access to affordable housing but also experience reduced energy costs. The prototype is shaped by a top-down governance framework, primarily led by state actors at multiple levels. This collaboration aims to take a central role in directly managing the building stock to achieve social and environmental objectives rather than relying on the market. The project represents an innovative

Summary table	Prototype of change
Name	Housing Thessaloniki
Location	Thessaloniki, Greece
Type of Prototype	Institution Driven – Policy Innovation
Focus	Energy use reduction through housing quality, affordable housing
Beneficiaries	Vulnerable households
Key Innovation	Combining upgrade empty housing stock to tackle housing and energy at the same time
Key outcomes	Housing vulnerable households, re-using empty existing housing stock

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and unique approach in its ownership structure. The apartments are administered under the oversight of the local public sector allowing the effective allocation of public resources for social purposes, enabling the state to reclaim vacant and abandoned properties.

Outcomes (Social, energetic, political)

As the project is still in its early stages, its outcomes are not yet measurable. It has three clear objectives: 1) to provide stable and affordable housing through social rent, 2) to reduce energy costs by implementing energy-efficient upgrades, and 3) to improve the overall quality of housing through es-

sential apartment renovations.

By offering rent reduction caps at 30% of social tenants' income, the project aims to provide these households with housing security and affordability. From the perspective of the energy transition, the results are currently less noticeable. The limited funding does not cover all stages of application and is expected to cease once renovations are completed. Additionally, the budget for the property is restricted (between €14,000 and €16,000), which creates significant

problems regarding the energy upgrades of the apartments and constrains the extent of improvements. They upgrade the dwellings to a class C energy rating. However, the programme does not incorporate renewable energy technolo-

Fieldwork conducted to-date: Housing Thessaloniki (Thessaloniki, GR - KIT)

Field research comprised of 31 qualitative expert interviews with the following profiles:

- **Policymakers:** Local state stakeholders including the municipality of Thessaloniki (5), the development agency of the city of Thessaloniki (4), the Municipality of Neapoli-Sykies (1), and the Municipality of Athens (1). Regional state stakeholders: the Regional Development Fund of Central Macedonia (1). Central state stakeholders: the Ministry of Social Cohesion and Family (2).
- **Consultants and Experts on Energy Transition:** Heinrich Boll Foundation (2), Association of energy engineers (1), the Cluster Bioeconomy and Environment of Western Macedonia, and the Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving (1).
- **Academics:** In total 6 interviews with experts with backgrounds in political science, architecture, economy and engineering.
- **Market actors:** From real-estate (2), construction and insulation companies (3).
- **Other participants:** Activists (3 also as before mentioned academics); the Architects' Association of Thessaloniki (1), a lawyer (1).

Most interviews were conducted both in person and online, following a semi-structured interview guide to allow for flexibility in the discussion. The field research was further supported by photographs, non-participant observation, and a memo containing notes on observations, discussions, and personal reflections.

gies such as solar panels or advanced heating systems. The programme is also limited as only 30 households benefit as part of this pilot.

Upscaling (replication, expansion, institutional effects)

There is strong political will and motivation among municipal actors, which is the key driver for advancing the project. The availability of public properties in the urban area of Thessaloniki presents additional opportunities for expansion, as many of these properties can be renovated and allocated to vulnerable households. Tackling the financial and technical challenges necessitates securing additional resources. However, it also illustrates how underutilised resources can be reimaged to tackle housing and energy challenges. Furthermore, integrating advanced technological expertise, such as energy-efficient retrofitting methods, is essential to enhance the overall impact of the project. Nonetheless, it might be challenging for other municipalities with fewer public assets or weaker institutional frameworks to adopt this model. It also requires substantial political commitment and collaboration between public bodies, NGOs, and private stakeholders. At national level, expanding the initiative would necessitate pivotal changes in policy frameworks to support social housing programmes. While Housing Thessaloniki could serve as a valuable reference for other urban environments at European and international levels, there is currently limited active initiative for scaling up and connecting to other similar projects internationally. As the pilot is still developing, it is also difficult to comment on its potential for institutionalisation or vertical scaling.

Karlsruhe

Institutional participatory

8.12. Prototype 12. Energy Districts (Karlsruhe, DE - KIT)

Short Description (who initiated, aims and focus, type of prototype)

The KfW432 subsidy, which existed in Germany between 2011 and 2024, enabled the implementation of energy districts within the financial program „energy efficient urban redevelopment” from the KfW bank. Federal funding was suspended for this program in 2024 despite its accessibility, openness, and low interest rates in its implementation. In Karlsruhe, the Karlsruhe Energy and Climate Protection Agency (KEK) intends to continue implementing the energy districts as a measure, which is included in the municipal energy plan. The KEK is a non-profit limited liability company, whose shareholders are the City of Karlsruhe and the municipal utilities. The energy districts were originally initiated by the city of Karlsruhe in the urban planning department. Its specific aim was the development of energy districts in combination with the redevelopment of particular urban areas. The KEK particularly focuses on providing advice and information to households in the energy districts. Initially this was done with employees going from household to household and making the offers, but now information stands are set up in the districts to advise offers. As part of a series of events called „KEK on tour”, the agency is offering online lectures for citizens on how to install heat pumps. In addition, they are also inviting citizens to guided tours in the district to show practical examples of energy-efficient modernization. The agency invites every household in the district

to be potentially part of an educational event via a postal letter box.

How does it address the Housing Energy Nexus (Green Energy, poverty, household type, tenancy)

The advice provided by the energy districts can be utilised by tenants, who receive housing benefits. Similarly, households in apartments that are subject to price and occupancy restrictions under the State Housing Promotion Act can benefit from these offers. However, only the owner of the apartment or building can undertake extensive technical changes, such as installing a heat pump or adding solar panels. The greatest potential for action, following initial awareness-raising and consultation by the KEK, is available to homeowners. In addition to this, feasibility studies on local heating supply are to be carried out within the existing energy districts.

Outcomes (Social, energetic, political)

KEK employees are prohibited from competing with energy consultants in the free market, hence the only options are to provide advice and raise awareness locally. According to

Summary table	Prototype of change
Name	Energy Districts
Location	Karlsruhe, Germany
Type of Prototype	Institution Driven and participatory
Focus	Promoting energy reduction measures
Beneficiaries	Home owners, renters to a lesser extent
Key Innovation	Area based approach to reduce energy needs
Key outcomes	Limited impact, primarily advice focussed

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a local politician, the work of the KEK on the ground in the neighbourhoods has, in the past, resulted in a dynamic that has led to an increase in the implementation of renewable energy technologies, such as new solar panels on rooftops. Inequalities, however, are rarely considered or addressed by the KEK.

Upscaling (replication, expansion, institutional effects)

The energy district measure can be easily copied by others by defining a geographical area in the city. They can be implemented at the local level every city of different sizes. Also internationally energy districts can and have been taken up by municipalities. An importance hindrance is the necessary involvement of different municipal stakeholders such as utilities, municipal departments, external service providers, and residents. The high coordination effort would require staff time and continuity. In terms of vertical up scaling or institutionalization, the possibilities are less clear. The concept of energy districts was already a federal project before it got taken up by the KEK.

Fieldwork conducted to-date: Energy Districts (Karlsruhe, DE – KIT)

For the fieldwork in Karlsruhe and the investigation of the energy districts prototype, we conducted 11 in-depth qualitative expert interviews, 4 semi-structured interviews with homeowners, and 2 workshops: one with tenants and another with individuals interested in the energy transition. The expert interviews included:

- Academics: 1
- Local policymakers: 4
- Municipal energy company: 1
- Municipal energy agency: 2
- Municipal housing company: 2
- Social welfare representative: 1

The semi-structured interviews were conducted on October 19, 2024, near an information stand of the Energy and Climate Agency in Karlsruhe. Homeowners interviewed were from Waldstadt (3) and Hagsfeld (1).

The first workshop was organised in collaboration with the Energy and Climate Agency in Karlsruhe and the Bürgerverein Waldstadt (Citizen Association Waldstadt) at the association's facility. Five participants attended: 2 scientists, 1 board member of the citizen association, and 2 students.

The second workshop was arranged in cooperation with the Mitmach-Laden, a community center run by the Badischer Landesverein für Innere Mission with 10 participants, mostly retirees and tenants. Of these:

- 5 were tenants of SOPHIA Karlsruhe, in apartments built by Volkswohnung GmbH.
- 1 lived in the Johann-Volm-Haus of the Karl Friedrich-, Leopold- und Sophien-Stiftung in Karlsruhe.
- For 2 participants, their tenancy or homeownership status in Waldstadt was unclear.
- 1 participant was not a resident of Waldstadt.

During the fieldwork, we engaged extensively in **non-participant observation** and **participant observation**, documenting thoughts, observations, and feelings in a 9-page fieldwork memo.

Conclusion and Outlook

PREFIGURE's core objective is to address the societal challenges discussed in this document by identifying, analysing, and comparing emerging "Prototypes of Change". These are alternative social, political, and economic initiatives which are aimed at promoting affordable housing renovations while tackling energy poverty and offering sustainable energy solutions. Through a combination of quantitative, qualitative, and ethnographic research, PREFIGURE examines these initiatives within their specific local social and economic contexts, fostering a deeper understanding of their potential to reshape housing and energy policies. The present report has assessed the scope and impact of these Prototypes of Change, thereby establishing the foundation for practical policy recommendations, comparative analysis and further development of learning communities involving stakeholders in each locality.

The PREFIGURE project is of critical importance in terms of establishing a conceptual connection between discourses rooted in Political Economy and Urban Political Ecology, demonstrating how the material and socio-political dimensions of urban transformations are deeply intertwined. By placing the interplay between housing and energy systems at the forefront, the project illuminates the structural inequalities embedded in contemporary urban governance while also demonstrating alternative models that challenge dominant property and energy regimes. A significant contribution of the project is the establishment of the Housing-Energy Nexus as a novel interdisciplinary concept. This concept captures the interdependencies between housing access, energy provision, and broader socio-environmental justice concerns. Situating this nexus at the core of its inquiry, PREFIGURE advances new theoretical and empirical insights into the pathways for transitioning toward just and sustainable urban futures. This approach enhances scholarly debates and provides a framework for policymakers, activists, and communities to envision and enact transformative change beyond conventional sectoral silos. The project contributes to academic discourse and lays the groundwork for actionable strategies aimed at fostering equitable and resilient urban societies.

In detail, the objective of PREFIGURE is to encourage a change in thinking epistemic dialogues, thereby facilitating a more profound comprehension of the way social, political, and market innovations have the potential to drive sustainable and energy-efficient housing transitions. The project aims to alleviate housing inequalities by promoting accessible solutions that ensure a fairer distribution of the social and financial burdens of energy transitions. In this context, PREFIGURE has the potential to generate transformative breakthroughs in several key areas:

- **Durable learning communities:** By fostering long-term collaborations among local, na-

tional, and regional policymakers, as well as civil society actors, the project strengthens shared knowledge and collective capacity for action.

- **Knowledge mobilisation:** Through co-production and dissemination of insights, PREFIGURE supports the implementation of sustainable housing renovations and energy-efficient upgrades.
- **Scaling of innovations:** By integrating social, market-driven, and political initiatives, PREFIGURE facilitates the expansion of innovative prototypes into inclusive and affordable housing policies.

Furthermore, the project is committed to enhancing the socio-economic and spatial integration of vulnerable, disadvantaged, and marginalised communities. By addressing structural inequalities at their root, PREFIGURE not only highlights the challenges these groups face but also contributes to shaping more just and inclusive urban environments. Through an in-depth analysis of income disparities, wealth distribution, and market polarization, the project deepens the understanding of how these factors influence housing real estate markets and perpetuate inequalities. The project equips decision-makers with robust, evidence-based insights, empowering them to design policies that challenge exclusionary patterns and promote equitable access to housing. In sum, the project serves as a catalyst for change, bridging research and action to build cities that are inclusive, resilient, and socially just.

The project employs a comparative analysis of housing policies, energy systems, and real estate markets across seven EU countries, complemented by in-depth case studies in seven local contexts. This approach offers valuable insights into how green and digital transitions affect housing inequalities, and how different user groups perceive and respond to these transitions. Moreover, the project fosters dialogues that connect citizens, social and economic stakeholders, and policymakers, thereby creating spaces for mutual learning and collaboration. Scientific evidence from the research will support the co-creation and acceleration of energy efficiency measures, while also prompting further reflection on how land use policies –particularly the construction of new housing– can better include vulnerable populations.

By framing sustainable housing transitions as a pathway to broader socio-economic transformation, PREFIGURE redefines how interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approaches can inform policy and practice. The project's multifaceted approach encompasses the generation of quantifiable indicators that illuminate disparities between owners and tenants, while concurrently fostering creative dialogues between bottom-up social, market-based, and political innovations. These interactions give rise to alternative policy solutions for addressing housing inequalities and guiding stakeholders, including housing policymakers, real estate actors, homeowners, and tenants, towards a just transition to low-emission, net-zero-energy housing.

The project's approach is characterised by its promotion of bottom-up innovation and the cultivation of dynamic networks of collaboration, thereby introducing a holistic, integrated strategy for addressing housing inequalities. It facilitates the exchange of knowledge, experiences, and strategies among diverse communities and decision-making spheres, fostering a collaborative environment. The creation of an innovative learning network is a key element of PREFIGURE's strategy, aimed at the co-development and implementation of forward-thinking policy frameworks and societal actions. These actions are designed to strengthen social

cohesion, empower marginalised groups, and lay the foundation for more just and sustainable urban futures. The project's approach, which integrates research, practice, and policymaking, positions it as a significant contributor to the transformation of housing systems. It aims to ensure that equitable access to housing and energy becomes a fundamental component of sustainable societies.

